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Project Summary

European musical heritage is a dynamic historical flow of experiences, leaving heterogeneous traces that are difficult to capture, connect, access, interpret, and valorise. Computing technologies have the potential to shed a light on this wealth of resources by extracting, materialising and linking new knowledge from heterogeneous sources, hence revealing facts and experiences from hidden voices of the past. Polifonia makes this happen by building novel ways of inspecting, representing, and interacting with digital content. Memory institutions, scholars, and citizens will be able to navigate, explore, and discover multiple perspectives and stories about European Musical Heritage.

Polifonia focuses on European Musical Heritage, intended as musical contents and artefacts - or music objects - (tunes, scores, melodies, notations, etc.) along with relevant knowledge about them such as: their links to tangible objects (theatres, conservatoires, churches, etc.), their cultural and historical contexts, opinions and stories told by people having diverse social and artistic roles (scholars, writers, students, intellectuals, musicians, politicians, journalists, etc), and facts expressed in different styles and disciplines (memoire, reportage, news, biographies, reviews), different languages (English, Italian, French, Spanish, and German), and across centuries.

The overall goal of the project is to realise an ecosystem of computational methods and tools supporting discovery, extraction, encoding, interlinking, classification, exploration of, and access to, musical heritage knowledge on the Web. An equally important objective is to demonstrate that these tools improve the state of the art of Social Science and Humanities (SSH) methodologies. Hence their development is guided by, and continuously intertwined with, experiments and validations performed in real-world settings, identified by musical heritage stakeholders (both belonging to the Consortium and external supporters) such as cultural institutes and collection owners, historians of music, anthropologists and ethnomusicologists, linguists, etc.

Executive Summary

Testing and validating ontologies, especially through competency questions, are crucial for ensuring the quality of ontologies and the Polifonia Knowledge Graph (PKG) in the Polifonia project. There are significant challenges in constructing KGs for the musical heritage knowledge engineering process. First, modern KGs are often built in a bottom-up fashion, lacking documents for Competency Questions (CQs) generation to evaluate KGs. Second, Knowledge engineers face these challenges amid various other top-down activities that have increased in complexity for obtaining requirements and CQs.

With the advent of contextual embedding-based language models and Large Language Models (LLMs), new methods for ontology testing have gained prominence, offering support for human-led ontology investigations. These approaches typically use plain text and unstructured data to generate competency questions. However, this method encounters limitations in formalizing and simplifying implicit domain knowledge, which are essential steps in creating effective competency questions for ontology testing.

To address these challenges, this deliverable introduces innovative frameworks: RevOnt, IDEA+, EODPs, and ontology documentation with LLM. RevOnt, available in our GitHub repository, is an automated framework designed to generate competency questions from Knowledge Graphs (KGs), using ground-truth datasets based on the WDV dataset. It leverages various language models and machine learning techniques to generate questions from Knowledge Graphs (KGs). IDEA+, on the other hand, facilitates interaction between domain experts and ontology engineers, utilizing LLMs as an intermediary interface. EODPs provide support to offer high-level schematic information in Wikidata. The ontology documentation method attempts to generate a set of comments and verbalizations for a class through its axioms using LLMs. These innovations aim to streamline the ontology testing process, reducing its complexity and reliance on human intervention.

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Table of contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Background	4
1.2	Our Contribution	6
2	Related Work	9
2.1	Ontology Engineering	9
2.2	LLM-based Ontology Engineering	11
2.3	LLM-based Ontology Documentation	12
3	Methodology	14
3.1	RevOnt Framework	14
3.1.1	The WDV dataset	16
3.1.2	Verbalisation abstraction	16
3.1.3	Question generation	20
3.1.4	Question filtering	21
3.2	IDEA+ Framework	25
3.3	Extraction of Empirical ODPs from Wikipedia	27
3.4	Ontology documentation using LLMs	29
3.4.1	The issue of documentation	29
3.4.2	Leveraging LLMs to comment an ontology	31
3.4.3	Verbalising a class through its axioms	32
3.4.4	Improving the comment through a LLM	33
4	Evaluation	36
4.1	The Evaluation of RevOnt’s Performance to Generate CQs	36
4.1.1	Dataset collection	36
4.1.2	Experimental results	39
4.1.3	Syntactic analysis of verbalisations and CQs	43
4.2	Examples of The IDEA+ Framework Implementation	50
4.3	Evaluation of automatic ontology documentation	54
4.3.1	Prompting the right way	54
4.3.2	Are generated comments reliable?	55
5	Conclusions	58
6	Compliance to FAIR principles	62
6.1	RevOnt – Software	62

6.2	WDV-CQ – Data	63
6.3	IDEA+ – Software	63

1 Introduction

One of the most important tasks in Polifonia is the construction of musical heritage knowledge graphs (KGs) to support the downstream tasks of the project. Building these KGs and the ontologies that support them is, however, challenging from a knowledge engineering perspective: the concepts and entities that need to be modelled come from a distributed, complex network of stakeholders with different backgrounds, specialisations, and domains (music theory, education, cultural heritage, computational musicology, data science). This complexity affects not only the tasks of conceptualisation and modelling, but also the evaluation of effectiveness of the resulting KGs. Traditionally, this evaluation has been based on the ability of the KGs to answer various **competency questions** (CQs) that are decided beforehand. However: (a) modern KGs are often built in a bottom-up fashion, and reuse existing KGs that do not have any documented CQs—therefore, deriving plausible CQs automatically from existing KGs would strength any evaluation process; and (b) they do so amid various other top-down activities that continue to exist and have increased in complexity, such as requirements collection and management, story and persona writing, maintenance of CQs, and deriving ontology modules from existing CQs. In addition, users can only successfully use the resources described in ontologies and KGs if the **documentation resources** they are accompanied with are of sufficient clarity and appropriateness; however, generating good quality documentation and at scale has become a challenging task, exacerbated by large-scale KG development efforts such as those we have seen in Polifonia. This deliverable describes various pieces of published research, **RevOnt** [1], the **IDEA+ framework** the **Empirical Ontology Design Patterns (EODPs)**, and **LLM-based ontology documentation**, which address these challenges and support the knowledge engineering process for the provisioning of high-quality CQs that can be used for better ontology testing and evaluation.

Knowledge engineering methodologies, especially for supporting ontology development, have been the subject of significant research in the Semantic Web field. Most methodologies [2–7] include a requirement elicitation phase and an ontology evaluation/testing phase, as fundamental in their processes. Requirement elicitation is the process of extracting and collecting requirements from domain and application experts, stakeholders, datasets, etc., whereas the evaluation phase deals with assessing the quality of the ontology. The basis of both these phases is the requirements, in the form of CQs. CQs play an important role in the ontology development life-cycle, as they represent the ontology requirements and are criteria for the evaluation of the ontology [8]. Despite the key role of the CQs in the process, there is no systematic mechanism to elicit them. Moreover, even though there are several methodologies that place CQs at the centre of the ontology evaluation [3, 8], there is a notable need for tool support for this phase of the process [9].

Generally, CQs are defined in a top-down approach, but the potential coming from existing KGs (e.g. Wikidata [10], DBPedia [11]) provides an opportunity to design a bottom-up approach to

extract CQs. Such an approach, which we propose in the RevOnt framework described in this deliverable, consists of reverse engineering an ontology, i.e. defining a method for extracting competency questions from existing KGs, rather than doing so from experts or other sources. This proposition is founded on the observation that recently an increasing number of knowledge engineering projects (e.g. Polifonia¹, SPICE²) have involved the construction of KGs from already existing ones; therefore, in many cases KGs are the starting point of knowledge engineering projects, rather than the end of the process. A direct application of the RevOnt is being able to query the knowledge graph of origin in order to understand its content. Modern KGs are built using a combination of human and automated actions (e.g. information extraction from text, data input from databases). Usually, these actions are not well-documented and derive an ontology that is not adequately structured [12]. Therefore, understanding what CQs a KG answers can support the development of its ontology, the KG's evaluation, documentation, and reuse.

Another application of the method can be to support the knowledge engineering process. We hypothesise that the requirement elicitation and the evaluation phases can be enhanced, both in terms of procedures and rules, and in terms of the quality of the outcomes, with such a method; here we propose a method to address the first step of such an hypothesis, namely, to reliably extract the CQs to which an existing KG provides answers. Regarding the requirement elicitation, the data from already existing KGs, which have greatly proliferated in the last years [13], can provide a different view of the domain of the ontology that is being constructed, complementary to the view provided by domain experts that are involved in the process or other sources. This additional information can improve the coverage of the domain, and in turn, of the ontology model. At the same time, the resulting CQs can later be used as criteria for the evaluation of the ontology. Motivated by the need for tool support for the knowledge engineering process, the opportunities that KGs offer in terms of application, and by leveraging recent advances in natural language processing, we raise the following research questions:

- **RQ1:** To what extent can CQs be extracted directly from existing KGs?
- **RQ2:** Which quality features can be inferred from human-made CQs and to what extent are these preserved in those extracted from a KG?

OE has long faced arguments about its technical challenges and costs. Despite the development of collaborative methodologies, the domain of the Semantic Web still struggles to positively impact the liveliness, evolution, and reusability of ontologies [14].

The rise of Large Language Models (LLM) is gaining significant attention from ontology and knowledge engineers due to their language understanding capabilities, which translate into generalisation across various tasks, multidisciplinary question answering, generating text at human levels of fluency and coherence, and dealing with ambiguity and long-range dependencies [15].

We hypothesise that LLMs can assist and facilitate OE activities to implement conversational workflows and prompt-driven tools that can reduce the complex interactions between domain experts and ontology designers, while accelerating the analysis and the formalisation of requirements. To confirm our motivations and collect insights for the design of such framework, we put

¹<https://polifonia-project.eu/>

²<https://spice-h2020.eu/>

forth the following research questions.

- **RQ3:** Which ontology engineering activities are the most in need of computational support?
- **RQ4:** How can LLMs enable a conversational ontology engineering framework to support these activities?

To address RQ3, we conducted a survey asking ontology engineers to rate OE activities in relation to their difficulty and the manual effort required. We reuse the insights collected from the survey to implement a conversational workflow where different categories of users interact independently with the system and produce intermediate artefacts and documentation throughout the various stages of the OE process (RQ4).

Another tool for ontology evaluation is the formalisation of patterns that the ontology or KG needs to adhere to. This can be seen as a set of constraints that the KG has to satisfy. However, the proliferation of large, distributed, collaborative KG construction efforts (e.g. Wikidata [10]) have made this type of constraints and patterns difficult to enforce. Still, entities tend to use similar properties to describe similar types of things, suggesting that a more bottom-up approach—in which constraints are extracted from the KG, rather than enforced top-down—should be feasible. Therefore, we ask the question:

- **RQ5:** How can Ontology Design Patterns be extracted in an empirical fashion from large, collaboratively, schema-less built knowledge graphs?

Finally, ontology documentation is a crucial step in knowledge engineering because it enables user understanding, agreement, and the ability to use ontological resources for the purposes for which they were originally intended

- **RQ6:** To what extent can we leverage LLMs to automatically generate ontology documentation without human intervention?

On the aforementioned applications, a well-defined knowledge graph serves as the backbone structure for generating CQs or ontology creation. The Wikidata knowledge graph encompasses a vast array of factual statements regarding entities and events across multiple domains. However, intuitively understanding the ontology structure implied in Wikidata can be challenging, as this underlying ontology is constructed through bottom-up approach and is partially implicit, subject to frequent updates by Wikidata editors. To tackle this issue, we have developed a method for extracting Empirical Ontology Design Patterns (EODPs) from knowledge graphs. These EODPs may be specific to certain domains and include data regarding the probability of emerging axioms/constraints. The EODPs serve to provide additional information into domain-specific ontology design patterns implied in the knowledge graph that are not explicitly present.

With the four research questions we raise, we describe the background of and our contributions of the RevOnt, IDEA+, EODPs, and ontology documentation using LLMs.

1.1 Background

The process for engineering an ontology starts with the requirement elicitation phase, as established in many methodologies such as [3–7]. An initial set of requirements is formalized and prioritized by ontology engineers. Based on the priority given to the competency questions, ontology engineers develop an ontology iteratively. The competency questions are simultaneously used for the testing of the ontology to ensure its quality. While the ontology is built and tested, the engineers construct the respective knowledge graph. A synthesis of the main steps in an ontology development process is displayed in Figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1: A synthesis of the main steps in an ontology development process

Based on our experience with eXtreme Design (XD)[3], requirement elicitation is an engaging task that includes continuous interactions with experts and data investigation. In-person or online meetings with domain experts generally need substantial planning and time for the ontology engineer to thoroughly grasp the domain. Meanwhile, the current tool support, like Google forms and GitHub templates, is inadequate to provide a consistent framework for gathering information. The process still needs time and effort from the ontology developer to analyse the information, structure it, and comprehend the input. The same techniques and constraints apply to extracting competency questions from data sets. It is critical to emphasise that competency questions must be of a specific quality to be utilised for the intended purpose. A competency question's fundamental quality check is that it must be translatable to a query that can help to validate the ontology. The transformation process from informal competency questions to formal competency questions lacks standardisation, is time-consuming, and requires a significant amount of effort.

An example of the requirement collection procedure based on XD comes from the Polifonia project³. First, we asked domain experts to create stories. In the context of the project, a story is a template for collecting requirements which might include information about the persona, the goal, the scenario, competency questions, and resources, described in detail by [16]. Given that domain experts often are not knowledge engineers, the competency questions that we received required a considerable amount of manual work to be transformed into formal competency questions. For instance, an informal competency question was *"In which historical documents is there evidence of a musical composition?"*⁴. This competency question was followed up by additional interaction with the domain experts to understand what the concept of evidence means to them, which in turn was defined *"as any direct linguistic sign that refers to concepts (name, or part of it)"*. This information was used to reformulate the competency question and have a formal one as follows *"Which historical documents mention a musical composition?"*.

This example demonstrates that the process that an ontology engineer has to complete for manually eliciting a competency question, formalising it, and transforming it to a query for evaluating the ontology is inefficient and demands substantial manual effort and considerable interactions.

The CQs are the most important factor in testing ontology quality, yet there remain many aspects of ontology engineering that need to be addressed to improve efficiency. In our previous studies on XD ontology engineering, we identified the process of the XD ontology engineering methodology as shown in Figure 1.2. This process is characterised by its iterative and incremental nature, is driven by requirements, involves interactions among multiple teams, incorporates the reuse of Ontology Design Patterns (ODPs), and includes testing. While the proposed RevOnt framework can facilitate the generation of requirements and the testing process, the remaining processes in ontology engineering are still cumbersome. In particular, the collaboration among domain experts from multiple teams can be a time-consuming and tedious task due to the need for iterative and incremental interactions. To support this process, we have proposed the LLM-powered IDEA+ framework, an interactive tool for domain experts that is based on user stories.

³The Polifonia project aims to support providers in revealing the content of value hidden in their digital objects, to support scholars in conducting research based on large, heterogeneous data sources and to enable citizens to access and understand Musical Heritage with all its complexity.

⁴The complete story is found in <https://github.com/polifonia-project/stories>

Figure 1.2: Overview of the XD ontology engineering methodology

1.2 Our Contribution

To support the aforementioned scenario, we leverage language models and investigate their use in the process of extracting competency questions from a knowledge graph. The main contributions of this deliverable are threefold:

1. RevOnt, a framework for automatically extracting competency questions from a knowledge graph⁵;
2. The WDV-CQ dataset, providing 1786 manually annotated competency questions and 1904 verbalisations from a subset of Wikidata triples, together with those automatically extracted by RevOnt;
3. An experimental evaluation of RevOnt, shedding light on the quality of the extracted CQs in relation to their corresponding human annotations;
4. IDEA+, a framework for supporting the interaction of ontology engineering among domain experts and ontology engineers based on the LLM.

RevOnt aims at reversing the ontology engineering process starting from the knowledge graph. In general, the knowledge graph development process involves extracting knowledge from identified data, thus implying essential knowledge for generating CQs [17]. The data from the KG is used to formulate questions by leveraging Natural Language Processing (NLP) models. The questions are evaluated and filtered with techniques described in Section 3.1. The filtering results in a set of core competency questions that describe the areas of the knowledge graph from which the triples were retrieved. These competency questions could be further used to e.g. generate respective SPARQL query templates, supporting the testing of the ontology. The approach of RevOnt is

⁵Implementation of RevOnt and data to reproduce the experiments available at <https://github.com/King-s-Knowledge-Graph-Lab/revont>.

to reuse a large set of triplets from KGs for generating new CQs rather than collecting informal CQs from ontology documents and domain knowledge. We assume that KGs already contain a significant amount of domain knowledge in a structured format that could be used as potential CQs, since KGs are constructed based on the collected CQs. An overview of the approach is shown in Figure 1.3.

Figure 1.3: An overview of the RevOnt approach with an example use case for ontology testing. This article covers the process of competency question extraction (and leaves “Provide SPARQL templates for formal CQs” as future work).

The knowledge graph we use to experiment and evaluate the method is Wikidata, which is a collaboratively-edited multilingual knowledge graph. Wikidata focuses on objects that represent any topic, concept, or object. Here, we chose Wikidata because: it is a popular knowledge graph; it reflects common knowledge on several domains; and it provides resources that help to evaluate the approach such as ID, label, description, and statements. The limitations of this use case remain in the fact that the knowledge graph is not domain-specific. An example data model in Wikidata is illustrated in Figure 1.4 for the triples related to Douglas Adams⁶.

IDEA+ is designed to facilitate interaction between domain experts and ontology engineers, leveraging a natural language interface powered by the LLM. Domain experts can submit their stories in plain text, and the LLM then processes these stories to understand the content and extract CQs. Additionally, ontology engineers can employ the LLM with tailored prompt designs for various stages of ontology engineering, including CQs generation, analysis, ontology creation, and

⁶Picture derived from <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q16222597>

Figure 1.4: Datamodel of a Wikidata item. The datamodel provides key information for a Wikidata item such as identifier, label, description, aliases, statements, and references.

testing. This approach can support the ontology engineering process by bridging the gap between domain experts and ontology engineers.

In the remainder of the deliverable, Section 2 summarises related works regarding ontology development methodologies with a focus on the concept of competency questions and related work on relevant fields of research such as ontology learning and schema induction. Section 3 describes the approach that RevOnt uses to extract competency questions from a knowledge graph. Section 4 presents the experimental setup and the results of the evaluation. Finally, Section 5 presents the reflections the work, provides indications for future work, and concludes the article.

2 Related Work

2.1 Ontology Engineering

The early works in **ontology engineering** surfaced at the beginning of the '90s with projects such as TOVE [18], Ontolingua [19], among others, described in [20]. Building upon these foundational projects, later efforts, including the Enterprise Model Approach [21] and METHONTOLOGY [22], emerged, drawing inspiration from and extending the pioneering works of the early '90s to the 2000s. These works, intending to define methodologies that are closer to engineering practices, are followed in the early 2000s [23] and [24]. After a decade, ontology development methodologies that include cyclic processes, continuous integration and testing as [2–7] emerge and become a shared practice among engineers. One of the common denominators between these works is the concept of competency questions, early defined in [25]. Based on several works such as [3, 26–32], the definition of competency question can be reasonably summarised as "a typical query that an expert might want to submit to a knowledge base of its target domain, for a certain task" [30]. The role of a competency question is twofold: (1) to drive the modelling of the ontology by serving as a requirement, (2) to assist the evaluation of the ontology by being expressed as a query. In our research, we use these criteria to evaluate the quality of the generated CQs.

In consideration of the method and techniques that are used in our work, relevant related fields of research are ontology learning, and schema induction and discovery. **Ontology learning** is a multidisciplinary field that extracts terms, concepts, properties, and relationships from unstructured text using approaches from several disciplines such as knowledge representation, natural language processing, machine learning, etc. Surveys in ontology learning such as [33], classify ontology learning techniques into three classes namely linguistic, statistical and logical. *Linguistic techniques* are based on language features and are commonly used for data preparation (speech tagging, parsing and lemmatisation) as well as various other ontology learning tasks such as knowledge extraction. Prime examples of such techniques are Text2Onto¹ and CRCTOL. *Statistical techniques* (C/NC value, contrastive analysis, clustering, co-occurrence analysis, term subsumption and ARM) rely entirely on statistics from the underlying corpus and overlook the underlying semantics. The majority of statistical approaches make substantial use of probabilities and are commonly utilised in early stages of ontology learning following linguistics preprocessing. Relevant tools that use statistical techniques are OntoGain [34], OntoLearn[35] and ASIUM[36]. Lastly, *Inductive logic programming* is a machine learning discipline that employs logic programming to generate hypotheses based on prior knowledge and a set of examples. Significant tools are Syndikate [37] and TextStorm².

¹<http://neon-toolkit.org/wiki/1.x/Text2Onto.html>

²<https://dwijottam-dutta.github.io/TextStorm/about/about.html>

With the rapid growth of RDF and KG data resources, numerous studies on ontology learning using RDF have been proposed. These studies can be categorised based on the approach adopted for utilising RDF in ontology learning. Some studies have leveraged RDF datasets to enhance the quality of ontology learning, given that ontologies may have limited instances and data values. Consequently, data-driven ontology learning techniques could easily encounter information scarcity issues. RDF datasets serve as a valuable resource for ontology learning due to their semi-structured nature and similarity to ontologies. It proposed a possibilistic approach for testing OWL (Web Ontology Language) axioms against RDF facts, specifically for testing the 'SubClassOf' relationship [38]. The ADOL [39] was designed for automatic domain ontology learning from textual data with RDFs in general-purpose Knowledge Graphs. It utilises RDF data to create semantic similarity with the ontology by comparing extracted words and relations to the RDF set. Conversely, Mid-Ontology has been introduced to automatically construct a simplified ontology from the RDF set of Linked Open Data (LOD) for the integration of different ontology schemata [40].

Lastly, surveys such as [41] and [42] present an overview of the state-of-the-art in **schema induction** and discovery, a research field dealing with the extraction or discovery of semantic schemas from unstructured or semi-structured data [43]. The research is motivated by the fact that the data in the semantic web, either expressed in RDF or JSON, are not based on a predefined schema. The most widely used techniques in the schema discovery approaches are machine learning (classification, clustering and frequent pattern mining) and formal techniques (Formal Concept Analysis, bisimulation). The surveys discuss valuable works regarding implicit and explicit schema discovery approaches by taking into consideration the target problem, techniques, features, input, output, and quality aspects.

Relevant surveys such as [44] and [45] describe **ontology summarisation** approaches that use centrality metrics (e.g. PageRank) to identify the most informative concepts/nodes or extract important subgraphs to facilitate query-testing for verifying requirements against accessible data. In contrast, a recent research related to the extraction of Common Conceptual Components³ from multiple Ontologies using Ontology Design Patterns⁴ is presented in [46]. The authors present a non-extractive method to assist in the comprehension and comparison of different ontologies. Starting with a corpus of ontologies, it uses community detection, word sense disambiguation, frame recognition, and clustering to automatically produce a catalogue of conceptual components and observable ontology design patterns. Further, in [47], the authors present a study for discovering Encyclopedic Knowledge Patterns (EKP)⁵ from Wikipedia⁶ page links. The patterns, according to the authors, may be used as lenses for exploring DBpedia⁷ or for developing new ontologies that inherit the data and textual grounding offered by DBpedia and Wikipedia. Data

³A conceptual component (CC) is a complex (cognitive) relational structure that a designer implements in an ontology by using classes, properties, axioms, etc.

⁴http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/wiki/Main_Page

⁵EKPs are Knowledge Patterns that are grounded in encyclopedic knowledge expressed as linked data and as natural language text.

⁶<https://en.wikipedia.org/>

⁷<https://www.dbpedia.org/>

linking can also benefit from EKPs by modulating the datasets to be linked.

Our research contributes to the field of knowledge engineering by enhancing the requirement elicitation, knowledge graph reuse, and ontology testing processes. The competency questions extracted with our approach can be used to develop and test an ontology. Furthermore, extracting competency questions from a KG can indirectly aid ontology reuse and ontology learning tasks, as this approach retrieves terms and relations through the use of natural language processing models and machine learning. For instance, a wealth of competency questions could assist in identifying the optimal and most suitable ontology by testing and validating the generated ontology throughout the ontology learning process. Moreover, RevOnt supports the extraction of a schema of a KG through its abstraction stage, where the natural language verbalisation of a triple is abstracted from the instance level to the class level.

2.2 LLM-based Ontology Engineering

Ontology Engineering has long faced arguments about its technical challenges and costs [14]. The rise of the Large Language Model (LLM) is gaining significant attention from ontology and knowledge engineers due to the LLM's outstanding capabilities in natural language processing, such as generalization across tasks, multidisciplinary question answering, generating text at human levels of fluency and coherence, and dealing with ambiguity and long-range dependencies [15, 48].

We investigated four approaches using the LLM in ontology engineering. The first approach involves generating additional, descriptive text using the LLM to represent domain knowledge. Secondly, researchers attempt to use the LLM to generate examples of classes, relations, or schemas. These two approaches rely on the basic functionality of the LLM as a text generator. The third approach is to use the LLM to determine the similarity between two components of ontologies based on text. The last approach is using the LLM to recommend essential explanations and components for specific ontologies by transforming them into plain text. The latter two approaches require the LLM to have inferencing capabilities, rather than just generating text [49].

In the context of ontology engineering, the LLM-based method is still underexplored. However, the representative studies in ontology engineering, such as ontology matching and alignment, are notable. [50] proposed an agent-powered, LLM-based design paradigm for ontology matching, using the LLM as the central manager to control the entire process through prompt engineering. [51] investigated the potential of the LLM in using concept labels, scoring thresholds, and structural contexts in ontology matching. [52] utilized the LLM as a text-based discriminator for ontology matching with different numerical reasoning processes, such as cardinality and confidence filters. [52] used the LLM as a text-based discriminator for ontology matching with different numerical reasoning processes such a cardinality and confidence filters. All of the studies agree that the LLM has a great potential in ontology matching, but it stil has significant problems to be addressed such as hallucination, poor non-linguistic reasoning, and high cost of fine-tuning.

There are very few studies on ontology construction and learning from text using the LLM. [53] proposed using the LLM to provide relevant subconcepts for defined concepts and to generate

textual descriptions of each generated concept. They insisted that the LLM can provide proper subconcepts and essential information, using the base or superconcept of the ontology as the seed for construction. Similarly, [54] investigated the possibility of automatically extracting and structuring knowledge from natural language text. They tested tasks such as term typing, taxonomy discovery, and non-taxonomic relation extraction. The results showed that the LLM performs well for all these tasks, but its performance on term typing is somewhat lacking.

2.3 LLM-based Ontology Documentation

Facilitating interoperability and understanding across different domains is one of the major advantages of the ontologies developed within the Semantic Web. The documentation of such ontologies is crucial for enhancing their utility [55] and ensuring a high-quality model. Manually curated documentation poses challenges in terms of time and human resources. As ontologies grow in size and complexity, it becomes difficult to compile sufficient documentation. This might hamper the quality of the model. Given the formal nature of OWL ontologies, verbalising ontologies from logical statements to a Natural Language form has been explored since the early years of OWL, such as in [56], with the aim of providing tools to document an existing ontology. The verbalisation of an ontology consists of generating natural language sentences that express the formal definition of a class. The generated sentences are not intended to serve as a comment, but by conveying the definition of the class they are acting as a form of documentation.

All the existing approaches in ontology verbalisation design a map that turns the axioms asserted in a class into sentences [56–62]. The way sentences are formed and composed characterises the method and impact the fluency of a verbalisation. In [55], one of the evaluation criteria for an ontology is its clarity: : “an ontology should effectively communicate the intended meaning of defined terms. Definitions should be objective. When a definition can be stated in logical axioms, it should be. Where possible, a definition is preferred over a description. All entities should be documented with natural language.” [55]. Similarly to our proposed approach, most of the automatic documentation and verbalisation approaches maximise the clarity of a sentence by maximising its fluency.

Several approaches have been followed. One of the most successful ones is to directly exploit the formalism of OWL and map it to a controlled language (CL), such as Attempto Controlled English in [56]. This approach is effective at increasing the clarity of an ontology [63], which proves its fitness as documentation [55].

The main issue of a CL is intrinsic to its nature. Simplifying language certainly results in easier generation, but it also reduces its expressivity. This is a problem in domain-dependant ontologies. To overcome this issue, other approaches do not restrict to CL, but rather design a pipeline to increase the fluency of the verbalised axioms.

One approach is to use formal grammars to convert a logical formulation into a sentence [57, 64], which accommodates the domain-specificity of an ontology. Others increase the fluency of verbalised axioms by carefully structuring the verbalised description [60, 65]. Both approaches require a significant effort to adapt to different domains.

The recent development of Large Language Models (LLMs) pushed the boundaries of the NLP field [66]. Domain-specific tasks that once required careful modelling can now be solved by exploiting the generalisation ability that emerges from the massive amount of textual information used to train LLMs. Models like ChatGPT⁸ can generate realistic documentation in programming tasks applications [67] as well as other domains, such as the medical domain [68].

Our approach exploits those features by extracting a verbalised version of a class, akin to the methods explained above, and converting them into fluent sentences by leveraging a LLM. We draw inspiration from other Knowledge Engineering tasks that have been shown to benefit from the use of those models, such as ontology alignment tasks [52, 69] or ontology augmentation tasks [70].

⁸<https://openai.com/chatgpt>

3 Methodology

In this chapter we introduce the RevOnt and IDEA+ frameworks. We describe in detail the processes that are used for generating CQs and supporting the collaboration between domain expert and ontology engineer.

3.1 RevOnt Framework

This section presents RevOnt, a framework for extracting competency questions from knowledge graphs. As depicted in Figure 3.1, this is divided into three stages: 1) verbalisation abstraction, 2) question generation, and 3) question filtering.

In steps, Verbalising a Knowledge Graph consists in generating grammatically correct natural language starting from inter-connected triple-based claims – formed of subject, predicate, and object, [71]. Here, the purpose of the *Verbalisation Abstraction* stage is to transform the verbalisation from the instance level to the class level. For example, given the triple verbalisation "Michael Jackson is a member of the Michael Jackson discography.", without the abstraction the generated questions are: "Who is a member of the Michael Jackson discography?" and "What is Michael Jackson a member of?". These questions are not competency questions because they ask for specific instances, and not classes or properties. Thus, there is a need to abstract the verbalisation into a more general form. To complete the task, the *Verbalisation Abstraction* stage begins with a dataset, which contains the verbalisations of triples from a knowledge graph, as an input. The dataset should include data about the subject, predicate, and object of the triple, descriptions of the instances, IDs that align them to a knowledge graph; and most importantly, the verbalisation of the triple. This information is necessary for the selection of the class in which the subject and the object of the triple is an instance of or a subclass of.

The second stage of the framework is *Question generation*. The aim of this stage is to generate three questions for each triple verbalisation. This choice of design is made to understand the types of competency questions that are generated when the method asks the model about different parts of the verbalisation sentence. Essentially, this stage generates questions based on the abstraction of the triple verbalisation (e.g. from "A music artist is a member of their own discography" to "Who is a member of a discography?"). Part of this stage is a grammar check task that corrects errors that are found in the questions to improve their quality.

Finally, the *Question filtering* stage deals with the quality check and reduction of CQs generated in the previous step. The main task of this stage is *question reduction*, to filter semantically equivalent competency questions (those entailing the same ontology requirements), and identifying meaningful groups based on their similarity. This stage is needed to identify a comprehensive yet minimal set of core competency questions from all the generated CQs.

Figure 3.1: An overview of the RevOnt framework. The first stage, Verbalisation Abstraction, generates the abstraction of a triple verbalisation. The abstraction is used as input in the second stage, Question Generation, to generate three questions per triple and perform a grammar check.

In addition, we conceptualise a further step that aims to map competency questions to their corresponding SPARQL queries; hence providing an additional validation step (a competency question that can be matched to a SPARQL query has higher chances of being correctly formulated). Nonetheless, here we focus on the extraction of CQs and leave the implementation of this last feature as future work.

Table 3.1 shows a list of NLP models, modules, datasets and services used for the implementation of the framework, their category and the stage where they are used. Our choices are motivated in the corresponding sections below.

Table 3.1: A list of the language models, modules, datasets, and services used in the RevOnt framework

Model	Category	Stage
WDV	Dataset	Input
MiniLM	LM	Verbalisation abstraction
Wikidata query service	Service	Verbalisation abstraction
T5	LM	Question generation
T5 Grammar Correction	LM	Question generation
BigCQ	Dataset	Question filtering
SBERT	LM	Question filtering
UMAP	Dim. reduction	Question filtering
HDBSCAN	Clustering	Question filtering

3.1.1 The WDV dataset

There are several datasets that provide verbalisations of data such as the T-REx¹ and WDV dataset² for Wikidata entries, WebNLG³ for DBPedia⁴ entries, NYT-FB by [72] and FB15K-237 by [73] for Freebase⁵, and so on.

A first implementation of RevOnt was achieved for Wikidata, by leveraging the WDV dataset [71]. This dataset provides verbalisations of Wikidata claims and it contains 7.6K unique triples. According to [74], WDV has considerably more entity types and predicates than comparable datasets, and it is intended to serve as a benchmark dataset for data verbalisation models used on Wikidata. WDV enables a tight coupling between single claims and text by directly connecting a triple-based claim to a natural language phrase. The WDV dataset contains verbalisation of claims from 20 different themes (or domains) from the most common like artist, sport teams, university to celestial body, chemical compounds, taxon, etc. The diversity of triple verbalisations in the dataset contributes to interesting results and imposes challenges as well. An example of a claim verbalisation from the *Airpot* theme is shown in Figure 3.2. The described claim verbalisation is structured in the form of key-value pairs. It provides RDF triple-related information including "*subject_label*" and "*subject_desc*", as well as claim-related information including "*theme_label*" and "*verbalisation*".

3.1.2 Verbalisation abstraction

The first stage of the RevOnt framework is the *Verbalization Abstraction*. Its role is to generate an abstraction of a triple verbalisation. The triple verbalisation of Knowledge Graphs refers to

¹<https://hadyelsahar.github.io/t-rex/>

²<https://github.com/gabrielmaia7/WDV>

³<https://gitlab.com/shimorina/webnlg-dataset>

⁴<https://www.dbpedia.org/>

⁵<https://developers.google.com/freebase>

A claim verbalisation from the WDV dataset

```
{
  "claim_id": "Q20451714$49CB1F7A-FC51-41CF-81EA-3EC1EC81AB5D",
  "rank": "normal",
  "subject_id": "Q20451714",
  "property_id": "P366",
  "subject_label": "Livramento Do Brumado Airport",
  "property_label": "use",
  "object_label": "general aviation",
  "subject_dec": "airport in Brazil",
  "property_desc": "main use of the subject (includes current and former usage)",
  "object_desc": "civil use of aircraft excluding commercial transportation",
  "subject_alias": ["SNLB"],
  "property_alias": ["function", "role", "mission", "purpose", "utility", "used for", "used in", "usage"],
  "object_alias": ["GA", "G/A", "genav", "civil aviation"],
  "object_datatype": "wikibase-item",
  "object": {"value": {"entity-type": "item", "numeric-id": 1571929, "id": "Q1571929"}, "type": "wikibase-entityid"},
  "theme_root_class_id": "Q1248784",
  "theme_label": "Airport",
  "verbalisation": "Livramento Do Brumado Airport is used by general aviation.",
  "verbalisation_unk_replaced": "Livramento Do Brumado Airport is used by general aviation.",
  "sampling_weight": 2.642857143,
  "annotations": {
    "fluency_scores": [5, 5, 2, 4, 3],
    "fluency_mean": 3.8,
    "fluency_median": 4.0,
    "adequacy_scores": [1, 0, 0, 0, 0],
    "adequacy_majority_voted": 0.0,
    "adequacy_percentage": 0.8
  }
}
```

A depiction of triple-related key & value from a claim

Figure 3.2: A claim verbalisation from the WDV dataset. For dataset provides the ID, rank, theme, and verbalisation of the claim. There are present also the label, description, aliases and ID of the subject, property and object of the triple.

converting RDF triples into natural language text by utilising their components and relationships. To perform the abstraction, it is necessary to recognise and categorise the entities present in the verbalisation. The initial intuition for this task was to use a Named Entity Recognition (NER) model. We experimented with language models such as Camembert-ner⁶, Camembert-base-

⁶<https://huggingface.co/Jean-Baptiste/camembert-ner>

multilingual-cased-ner-hrl⁷, Ner-english-large⁸, Bio-Ner⁹ and the SpaCy library. The performance of each of these models was not satisfactory for 50% of the themes of the dataset.

Therefore, we designed a novel method to abstract the subject and object of a triple to the most similar-to-context Wikidata class. The procedure is shown in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Abstraction of a Wikidata triple

```
1: procedure TRIPLE VERBALISATION ABSTRACTION
2:   Create the sentence embedding of the subject description
3:   Create the sentence embedding of the object description
4:   Retrieve the Wikidata classes of the subject and object of the
   triple
5:   for each class do
6:     Get the synsets
7:     for each synset do
8:       Get the synset definition
9:       Create the sentence embedding of the synset definition
10:      Calculate the cosine similarity between the synset
   definition embedding and the subject/object descriptions'
   embeddings
11:  return Most similar synset
```

For each triple, the method extracts the sentence embeddings of the descriptions of the subject and the object using the MiniLM language model¹⁰. MiniLM is a sentence-level transformer model [75] that maps sentences to a 384-dimensional dense vector space. By leveraging a pre-trained language model¹¹, MiniLM is fine-tuned on a number of datasets¹² using a contrastive objective. Intuitively, a contrastive loss is used to minimise the cosine similarity between similar sentence pairs, while maximising that of other sentences in the same batch.

In the next step, RevOnt selects the English label of Wikidata classes using two properties of 'instance of' or 'subclass of' for entities. The query that we use for selecting this information from the knowledge graph is shown below. For this task, we use the Wikidata Query Service¹³. Wikidata Query Service is an implementation of a SPARQL server, based on Blazegraph¹⁴ engine. This is used to service queries for Wikidata and other datasets.

```
SELECT DISTINCT ?cLabel
```

⁷<https://huggingface.co/Davlan/bert-base-multilingual-cased-ner-hrl>

⁸<https://huggingface.co/flair/ner-english-large>

⁹<https://github.com/librairy/bio-ner>

¹⁰<https://huggingface.co/sentence-transformers/all-MiniLM-L6-v2>

¹¹<https://huggingface.co/nreimers/MiniLM-L6-H384-uncased>

¹²https://www.sbert.net/docs/pretrained_models.html

¹³<https://query.wikidata.org/>

¹⁴https://github.com/blazegraph/database/wiki/Main_Page

```
WHERE {{
    wd:{id} wdt:P31/wdt:P279? ?c .
    ?c rdfs:label ?cLabel .
FILTER(LANG(?cLabel) = "en") }}
```

For instance, for the triple verbalisation "*Michael Jackson is a member of the Michael Jackson discography.*", according to the dataset shown in Figure 3.2, the subject is *Michael Jackson* and the object is *Michael Jackson discography*. The respective descriptions are *American recording artist; singer and songwriter (1958-2009)* and *Wikimedia artist discography*. RevOnt extracts the sentence embeddings of the subject and object description and queries the Wikidata KG to select the classes of the subject and object of the triple. The result for *subject* is shown in Example 3.1.1.

Example 3.1.1. *The Wikidata classes for the subject "Michael Jackson"*

```
['human', 'natural person', 'omnivore', 'person',
'mammal', 'Homo sapiens']
```

Once classes are retrieved, RevOnt gets the corresponding Wordnet synsets for each class. Wordnet is a large electronic lexical database for English [76]. Cognitive synonyms (synsets) are groups of nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs that each communicate a separate notion. Synsets are linked together via conceptual-semantic and linguistic relationships. In Example 3.1.2 we present the respective synsets of the classes where "*Michael Jackson is an instance of/subclass of*". For each synset, it retrieves the definition and computes its sentence embeddings by using the MiniLM model.

Example 3.1.2. *The synsets of the Wikidata classes*

```
{ [Synset('homo.n.02')],
[],
[Synset('omnivore.n.01'), Synset('omnivore.n.02')],
[Synset('person.n.01'), Synset('person.n.02'),
Synset('person.n.03')], [Synset('mammal.n.01')],
[] }
```

In the last step, RevOnt calculates the cosine similarity between the embeddings of the definition of the synsets of each class with the embeddings of the description of the subject or object. The cosine similarity is calculated with the help of the Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK). NLTK is a suite of Python modules providing many NLP data types, processing tasks, corpus samples, and readers, together with animated algorithms, tutorials, and problem sets [77]. For the example shown above, the Wikidata class that is the most similar to the description of the subject *Michael Jackson* is *human*. As for the object of the triple, the Wikidata class is *discography*.

The values that the algorithm 1 returns populate a Python dictionary that is used for the abstraction task. More specifically, the subjects/objects and their corresponding most similar-to-description wikidata class are added to a dictionary, as shown in Example 3.3. The pattern means a list of classes and entities acquired in a execution of the algorithm 1.

Example 3.1.3. *The pattern dictionary*

```
{'Michael Jackson': 'human',  
'Michael Jackson Discography': 'discography'}
```

This dictionary is used to replace the subject and the object in a triple with the respective class. To continue on the same example above, the result of the verbalisation abstraction is presented in Example 3.1.4. This concludes the first stage of the framework, and the abstracted verbalisations are passed on to the second stage, Question generation.

Example 3.1.4. *The abstraction of the verbalisation*

```
Verbalisation: Michael Jackson is a member of the  
                Michael Jackson discography.  
Abstraction:   Human is a member of the discography.
```

3.1.3 Question generation

After the abstraction of the verbalisation, the next stage of the approach is to generate questions. Given a triple verbalisation where entities have been generalised, the goal is to automatically generate a set of questions addressing the content of the verbalisation. For this task, we have used the Text-to-Text Transfer Transformer (T5) [78] fine-tuned on the Stanford Question Answering Dataset (SQuAD) [79] for question generation. This was achieved by prepending the answer to the context. The specific T5 instance we used is labelled as `t5-base-finetuned-question-generation-ap`¹⁵. Notably, [80] demonstrated that this model can be handle generative tasks such as abstractive summarisation, classification tasks such as natural language inference, and even regression tasks.

To generate questions, the model requires as input a context (sentence) and an answer as a desired example . When an answer is not provided, the model will generate a question that is answered by the object of the sentence. For each triple, we have provided the model with the abstraction of the verbalisation as the context, and three answers: the class of subject, the property, and the class of the object. In most observed cases, when the class of subject and the class of the object are the answers, the questions that are generated are inverse in relation to each other; hence they may provide complementary requirements for the triple. As for the cases when the property is the answer, the questions that are generated are often the same as the ones

¹⁵<https://huggingface.co/mrm8488/t5-base-finetuned-question-generation-ap>

when the answer is the class of the object, but there are also many cases when the questions are quite interesting and not so straightforward. This behaviour of the model can be explained with the distance between the triple and the verbalisation. As noticed in the example below, while the property of the triple is `discography`, this property is not present in the verbalisation. This is the case for the majority of the verbalisations present in the dataset. In Example 3.1.5, we show the results of the Question Generation stage given the abstraction from Example 3.1.4.

Example 3.1.5. Question generation

Context: Human is a member of the discography.

Answer 1: human

Question 1: What is a member of the discography?

Answer 2: discography

Question 2: What is the relationship between
a human and a discography?

Answer 3: discography

Question 3: What is a human a member of?

Once the questions are generated, RevOnt performs a grammar check to detect and fix errors. This task is performed by the T5 Grammar Correction model¹⁶. Trivially, the model generates a revised version of the given text with the goal of addressing grammatical errors. It is trained with Happy Transformer¹⁷ using the JFLEG dataset [81].

3.1.4 Question filtering

In this section, we cover the third and last stage of RevOnt, which consists in filtering the questions that are generated from the second stage. This is achieved through *question reduction*, which is divided into two parts: paraphrase detection (to remove equivalent questions) and question clustering (to identify groups of similar requirements).

As some of the questions generated in the previous steps may be redundant, or show negligible semantic variations that are of little interest to ontology engineers, we filter out questions based on their similarity. This has two potential benefits: (i) it mitigates the noise and the artifacts introduced in the previous steps (e.g. questions with unclear or inconsistent semantics); (ii) it reduces the number of competency questions that will be presented to the ontology engineers. Depending on the desired level of filtering, here we provide two methods to identify groups of related questions.

- *Similarity grouping*, which aims at detecting groups (or clusters) of semantically similar – yet not necessarily identical, questions.
- *Paraphrase detection*, a specialisation of the former task focused on detecting questions with exactly the same meaning (e.g. “Is Batman a friend of Robin?” and “Is Batman Robin’s friend?”).

¹⁶<https://huggingface.co/vennify/t5-base-grammar-correction>

¹⁷<https://github.com/EricFillion/happy-transformer>

If the goal is to retain the largest number of questions, for example, because the ontology should model the domain at a granular level, the latter filtering method is more indicated. Instead, similarity grouping operates a more drastic reduction based on the relatedness of questions; which is also useful to get a high-level overview of the domain of interest.

Both our methods use sentence-level embeddings, rather than word-level representations, meaning that a sentence (in our case, a question) is mapped to a feature vector of a fixed size. The latter can be considered as a point in a high dimensional space providing a numerical summary of the sentence's meaning. In particular, here we leverage Sentence-BERT [75], an adaptation of BERT using Siamese and triplet network structures to derive semantically meaningful sentence embeddings.

Similarity grouping. The identification of questions with similar meaning is achieved via clustering of their embeddings – an application of unsupervised learning.

Following the projection of questions into the embedding space, dimensionality reduction is first applied using Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) [82]. This step is meant to preserve the consistency of distance measures over the embedding space due to the curse of dimensionality [83]. In general NLP tasks, sentences are encoded as numerical vectors to accurately measure the similarity among them in a distributional space. The size of these vectors, known as the dimension, determines a sort of resolution of the similarity measure. However, an excessively high dimension of embedding vectors can negate the similarity measure due to the curse of dimensionality. Thus, many Machine Learning (ML) processes typically perform a dimensionality reduction step after vector creation to mitigate the curse of dimensionality, which could adversely affect the ability of ML algorithms to distinguish among samples.

In addition, compared to other dimensionality reduction approaches, UMAP is effective for both visualisation and is more effective at preserving the global structure of the data (e.g. t-SNE is often suitable for visualisation only).

Similar questions are then detected using Hierarchical Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (HDBSCAN) [84] on the dimensionally-reduced representations. The choice of this algorithm is motivated by the fewer hyper-parameters, its robustness to noise, and the ability to deal with variable-density clusters (e.g. competency questions forming groups of heterogeneous size). Most importantly, as a density-based method, it does not require specifying the number of clusters a priori, and does not make any assumption on the shape of clusters. This is particularly suitable for finding groups of competency questions that are automatically extracted in the previous steps, as no assumptions can be made on the number and shape of their clusters. Notably, the same approach was adopted in IDEA+ [16] to cluster manually curated competency questions, and support participatory workflows for their refinement.

An example of competency question clustering is described in Figure 3.4. This figure depicts the clustering results of competency questions under the 'WrittenWork' theme following UMAP reduction. The grey cluster encompasses simpler competency questions related to object or subject identification in triples, while the yellow cluster is related to querying numerical values of birthdays for specific characters. The analysis of grey clusters reveals structural redundancies in competency questions. For example, the questions "What is Limassol located?" and "Who

founded Salinas?” within the grey cluster exhibit a similar structure. Through similarity grouping based on clustering, redundancy in competency questions with similar structures can be reduced.

Figure 3.3: Example of competency question clustering with annotations linking questions to their respective clusters for the 'WrittenWork' theme.

Paraphrase detection. Alternatively, if the goal is to filter out only those questions that have the same meaning – thereby avoiding duplicated entries, we look at paraphrase detection. One approach is to define a threshold on the cosine similarity of two sentence embeddings to deem them as semantically equivalent (e.g. considering two sentences as equivalent if they exceed a threshold t_{sim}). However, as demonstrated in Figure 3.4 for $t_{sim} = 0.8$ (a typical similarity threshold in NLP), this is not reliable for paraphrases, as it introduces a large number of false positive and negatives.

We address the detection of equivalent questions via transfer learning. In this case, given two questions, their sentence-level embeddings are fed to a feed-forward neural network for *paraphrase detection* – a binary classification task. The artificial neural network (ANN) is thus trained to predict whether two sentences are semantically the same (positive pairs, $y = 1$) or not (negative pairs, $y = 0$).

Despite the availability of datasets for paraphrase detection, which have been extensively used for representation learning, we did not find a pre-trained model for question-based paraphrase

Figure 3.4: The Distribution of cosine similarities per positive (blue) and negative (orange) question pairs. The vertical blue line denotes a similarity threshold (0.8) commonly used to consider 2 sentences/embeddings as highly related.

Figure 3.5: Architecture of the ANN for paraphrase detection. Dotted lines denote parameter-sharing, the plus symbol stands for additive feature fusion, and the rounded box repeats the same stack of layers for 3 times before binary classification.

detection. Therefore, we implemented a deep neural network that leverages sentence-level embeddings of questions to classify them as equivalent or different. The architecture is illustrated in Figure 3.5. First, the sentence-level (SBERT) embeddings of two questions are passed to linear projection layers with shared parameters. This is expected to fine-tune the embeddings on the question domain, without altering their dimension. An early fusion mechanism is then used to combine the 2 projected embeddings vectors through Hadamard product (element-wise product). The resulting vector, which still preserves the same SBERT embedding dimension, is then passed to 3 blocks of: fully-connected layers, followed by batch normalisation [85], ReLU activations, and dropout [86]. In the final layer, a sigmoid layer is used for binary classification. By sampling from the learned Binomial distribution, the model can then be used to classify whether two questions (given their embeddings) are equivalent or not.

3.2 IDEA+ Framework

First of all, our aim is to identify which activities/tasks are the most critical and time-consuming in an ontology design project involving 17 participants, all experienced in designing and developing ontologies. We have identified four activities/tasks that participants believe require support in ontology engineering.

The first one is the collection of requirements from domain experts. This is because the process of transforming implicit and underlying domain knowledge into explicit and formalized knowledge is a non-trivial task. The second one is the extraction of CQs from requirements. These requirements are typically described in plain text, consisting of one or two sentences that include specific domain terms. To test the ontology, it should be represented in simple and abstract CQs. The third activity is the retrieval of example data for completing the ontology by inputting data values. This step is crucial for testing the constraints or rules beyond the conceptual reasoning of the ontology. The last one is ontology testing, which is a tedious task involving the evaluation of the ontology’s quality using the generated CQs and domain experts’ knowledge.

1. Collection of requirements from domain experts and stakeholders.
2. Extraction of competency questions from (textual) requirements.
3. Retrieval of example data.
4. Ontology testing.

With the main activities identified, we designed the IDEA+ framework based on the LLM, which powers a collaborative ontology engineering system as shown in Figure 3.6. First, we utilize the LLM to collect requirements from domain experts. In this step, IDEA+ adopts a user story interface to simplify the activity of requirement description. The LLM assists in extracting these requirements from the provided user stories. Next, ontology engineers collaborate with domain experts to generate CQs using user stories and requirements extracted by the LLM. Ontology engineers can then refine and reformat the generated CQs with the assistance of the LLM to create the ontology. In this step, the LLM also aids in identifying missing information or knowledge from the domain experts. Subsequently, ontology engineers create the ontology using the refined CQs and extracted requirements. Lastly, ontology testing is performed by the engineers with the help of the LLM, which assists in identifying mismatches and discrepancies in the concepts from a linguistic perspective.

Figure 3.6: The process of IDEA+ for the LLM-powered collaborative ontology engineering system

To support the user story generation process, we have designed a story creation workflow, as illustrated in Figure 3.7. The workflow is divided into two parts: specification and refinement, to facilitate collaborative story creation. Before providing a user story to the LLM, the LLM’s behavior must be set up by designing prompts that include an assistance role and previous Q/A sequences. In the specification part, domain experts interactively share their requirements, consisting of some texts, with the LLM. The LLM then generates draft user stories based on these requirements. Domain experts review these draft stories and provide feedback to the LLM, which helps in generating improved user stories.

Figure 3.7: LLM-powered IDEA+: Story creation workflow

The IDEA+ framework is designed to extract CQs from user stories using the LLM, as depicted in Figure 3.8. Initially, the LLM produces the first version of CQs from the user story. However, the RevOnt framework can also be employed for CQ generation as an alternative to the LLM. The choice between these frameworks depends on the specific situation; for instance, if there are sufficient RDF dumps available for the given user story, the RevOnt framework might be the better choice for generating CQs. To assess the quality of the first version of CQs and to decide on the most appropriate framework, the expertise of an ontology expert is required. In the refinement steps, the IDEA+ framework iteratively generates CQs and evaluates the candidates. If certain candidate CQs are not finalized, they are included in a named entity substitution process to prevent their re-evaluation in future iterations.

Figure 3.8: LLM-powered IDEA+: Story creation workflow

Examples for testing ontology are crucial in establishing the foundation for ontology qualification. Ideally, these should be generated from scenarios or datasets pertinent to the specific situa-

tions the ontology aims to model. However, finding appropriate instances and individuals from a dataset that align with the identified requirements can be challenging and time-consuming, as some examples may be either too specific or too broad. To address this, we employ the LLM for generating simple examples from competency questions, as illustrated in Figure 3.9. This process is straightforward. We utilize the LLM's implicit knowledge to generate general concepts and then substitute them with named entities.

Figure 3.9: LLM-powered IDEA+: Story creation workflow

Lastly, the IDEA+ framework facilitates ontology testing using the LLM. Typically, ontology engineers test the ontology using SPARQL queries and CQs. While SPARQL is an effective language for managing an ontology in a structured code style, it requires engineers to transform CQs into the SPARQL format for testing. This transformation is time-consuming as it involves mapping the CQs and components of the ontology to the designed structure. Moreover, it does not account for the semantic similarity between the words in CQs and the ontology. To address these challenges, we propose a method for LLM-powered, SPARQL-free ontology testing.

LLM-powered SPARQL-free ontology testing has three steps. The process begins with a textual verbalization of the given ontology where classes, named entities, relations, and restrictions are described in plain text. Following this, a prompt is created by concatenating the verbalization with a request that guides the model in the extraction of competency questions, along with additional examples of good competency questions, akin to those used for stories. Finally, the competency questions inferred by the model are compared with the original ones. The overlap is measured in terms of coverage or overlap based on similarity. Any missing requirements discovered through this comparison are then notified to the Organizational Development team.

3.3 Extraction of Empirical ODPs from Wikipedia

The Wikidata knowledge graph includes a wide number of factual statements about entities and events in the real world, and is built collaboratively and is edited on a daily basis. As for other knowledge graphs, Wikidata contains statements about its schema, e.g. properties or classes of entities. However, these ontological constructs are defined in an underlying ontology whose definition is bottom-up and partially implicit. Moreover, this ontology is always subject to change due to frequent updates by Wikidata editors.

For these reasons, it can sometimes become challenging to understand the content of the KG, and to reuse it for specific use cases [87–89]. In this context, it becomes useful to exploit the knowledge graph data level to derive axioms or constraints of an *inferred* ontology.

Wikidata provides some flexible guidelines around use, namely:

- property constraints: rules on a property that specify how the property should be used in the knowledge graph, with possible exceptions; their definition is informal, without an explicit logical specification, thus they can still be violated or ignored;
- properties for this type: a property that allows to list the properties recommended to be used for instances of a certain class; however, Wikidata does not provide a mechanism to specify the appropriate range(s) to be paired with that specific domain;
- Type of Wikidata property: a metaclass, linked to a topic, with some relevant properties as instances; however, this is work in progress;
- Wikidata schemas: ShEx schemas that can be used for the validation of subsets of items inside the Wikidata KG; however, many domains are not covered yet, and it is rare that these constraints express the suggested range;
- Properties list in a WikiProject: in the context of domain-specific projects, some relevant properties to be used for that domain can be listed; however, the process of defining such properties for a domain is manual, and possible ranges for properties are not always specified, and, in any case, not in a formal way.

Clearly, there is room to give additional guidance on how to use the ontology underlying Wikidata. Based on the assumption that identifying ontology design patterns from a knowledge graph contributes to making its (possibly) implicit ontology emerge, we developed a method for extracting what we name *empirical ontology design patterns* (EODPs) from a knowledge graph¹⁸. These patterns may be specific to a certain domain, based on the (sub)KG being processed, and consist of frequent domain-property-range triplets, accompanied by statistics of their usage. Indeed, these EODPs include data about the probability of emerging axioms/constraints *happening*. They are formalized both as (i) *probabilistic* ontology design patterns, using RDF-star, as sets of axioms that are assigned a probability value based on their actual usage in the KG; and (ii) *probabilistic* ShEx shapes, as sets of constraints annotated with their probability by comments. Using the Wikidata knowledge graph as a use case, we demonstrate how these EODPs provide additional information about a domain-specific part of the KG, information that is not present in the existing guidelines.

We apply this method on two domain-specific subgraphs from Wikidata (considering 3 different versions of it, with an interval of 15 months in between.), addressing the *music* and *art, architecture, and archaeology* domains. Then, we compare the empirical ontology design patterns we extract with the current usage support provided by Wikidata. The example illustrated in Figure 3.10 depicts an instance of EODP for the 'album'.

In this way, we show that our method is domain independent, and we demonstrate how these

¹⁸The paper submitted to the Semantic Web Journal can be found here: <https://www.semantic-web-journal.net/content/empirical-ontology-design-patterns-and-shapes-wikidata>

Figure 3.10: An example of EODP for the album from Wikipedia portion on the music domain

patterns can provide guidance for the use of the Wikidata ontology and its potential improvement, and can give insight into the content of (domain-specific parts of) the Wikidata KG.

3.4 Ontology documentation using LLMs

3.4.1 The issue of documentation

The lack of documentation in existing ontologies is a widespread issue. To better assess the impact of this problem, we analyse the documentation of publicly shared ontologies on Github. Ontologies are retrieved by searching for files tagged as Web Ontology Language or Turtle, which include the terms `owl:Ontology` and `owl:Class`¹⁹.

Listing 3.1: SPARQL query to extract comments of each class.

```
PREFIX owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#>
PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>

SELECT DISTINCT ?class ?comment
WHERE {
```

¹⁹This is done by using the queries `owl:Ontology AND owl:Class language:"Web Ontology Language"` and `owl:Ontology AND owl:Class language:"Turtle"`

```
?class rdf:type owl:Class .
OPTIONAL { ?class rdfs:comment ?comment }
}
```

For each retrieved ontology, we extract the classes and their respective (optional) comments using the SPARQL query in Listing 3.1. Comments are optional since they might be missing. We extract a total of 1914 ontologies, with a mean of 33.89 and a median of 12 classes for each ontology. The biggest ontology contains 937 classes while the smallest one contains 1 class.

Figure 3.11: Distribution of comments in the analysed ontologies. Figure 3.11a described the total number of classes in the ontologies in logarithmic scale. Most of the ontologies found on the web are small, with ≤ 200 classes. Figure 3.11b shows the ratio $\frac{N_c}{N}$. Most ontologies do not have any comment at all.

In Figure 3.11 statistics of the data are shown. Most notably, the vast majority of the ontologies do not involve a large range of classes; 90% of all the ontologies have less than 82 classes in total, as can be seen in Figure 3.11a. Note that, while in principle a small ontology is quicker and easier to document, this does not result in a positive documentation trend. In Figure 3.11b we compute the ratio of commented classes $\frac{N_c}{N}$ where N is the total number of classes in the ontology and $N_c \leq N$ is the number of classes that have a comment asserted. The majority of the ontologies don't have any comment. On average only the 33.46% of the classes in an ontology have a comment. It is easy to see how this hampers the interoperability between different data sources claimed by the use of an ontology. Notably, we find a positive Pearson correlation ($\rho = 0.51$) between the number of classes on an ontology and their comments. The reason might lie behind the maturity of bigger ontology. In general, bigger ontologies undergo many iterative refinement steps, and it is easy to imagine a continuous update and integration to comments. Nonetheless, our analysis clearly proves that most of the publicly available ontologies on the web lack a sufficient amount of documentation.

3.4.2 Leveraging LLMs to comment an ontology

In this section, we describe in detail our approach to the generation of comments. To quantitatively evaluate the accuracy of our method we compile a dataset of class and comments pairs. We extract 100 classes from each ontology, together with their axiomatisation. We define the axiomatisation of an ontology class as the union of the selectional restrictions, subclass and superclass axioms together with all the properties in which the class appears as domain or range. For each class, we extract 3 additional classes that can be used as a reference during the generation process.

Ontology	Description	Avg words	Avg axioms
ArCo [90]	ArCo is the Italian Cultural Heritage KG, built on top of a network of 7 vocabularies.	34.64 ± 44.43	3.88 ± 2.68
DBPedia [91]	DBpedia is a KG compiled by extracting structured information from Wikipedia.	17.59 ± 15.65	3.26 ± 8.76
DOLCE [92]	DOLCE is the first foundational ontology axiomatised, inspired by cognitive and linguistic considerations.	55.16 ± 86.71	5.42 ± 7.09
FoodOn [93]	FoodOn is a comprehensive ontology about food, that accurately and consistently describes foods commonly known in cultures from around the world.	35.03 ± 18.99	1.77 ± 0.93
FRBR [94]	FRBR is a model intended as a generalised view of the bibliographic universe, independent of any cataloguing code or implementation.	10.17 ± 0.38	7.97 ± 5.17
GO [95]	The Gene Ontology resource (GO) provides structured, computable knowledge regarding the functions of genes and gene products.	22.67 ± 28.49	0.62 ± 1.16
HeLiS [96]	HeLiS is an ontology aiming to provide a representation of both the food and physical activity domains enabling the monitoring of users' actions and their unhealthy behaviours.	9.50 ± 4.24	1.44 ± 0.99
Schema.org [97]	Schema.org is a set of vocabularies in widespread use by both publishers and consumers of structured data on the Web.	16.31 ± 16.27	1.18 ± 0.41

Table 3.2: Set of ontologies used to compile the dataset.

We select 8 ontologies to compile our dataset, which are listed and described in Table 3.2. For each ontology, we report the average number of words in each comment and the average number

of axioms. Some ontologies, such as DOLCE and ArCo have comprehensive comments, as can be seen by the average number of words for each class. A similar argument holds for the axiomatisation, where DOLCE and FRBR on average have a high number of axioms while other ontologies, such as Schema.org or the Gene Ontology, have much less.

3.4.3 Verbalising a class through its axioms

Each class extracted from the ontologies of Table 3.2, alongside their reference examples, is coupled with a description derived from the axioms asserted in that class. As previously addressed, we take into account subclasses and superclasses, extracted employing the `rdfs:subClassOf` property, properties where the class appears as range, using the `rdfs:range` property, and where it appears as domain, using the `rdfs:domain` property.

Figure 3.12: Descriptions of a class from the FoodOn ontology (Figure a) and from the DOLCE ontology (Figure b). The yellow box represents a class. The blue boxes (above) represent superclasses, the green boxes (left) represent property where the class appears as domain and the purple boxes (right) represent the range properties.

Figure 3.12 shows an example of descriptions applied to two classes, one from the FoodOn ontology (Figure 3.12a) and one from the DOLCE ontology (Figure 3.12b). The descriptions are extracted by serialising the subclass axioms to string using Manchester syntax [98], while the object of the domain and range properties are added respectively at the start and the end of the property’s label. The generated sentence describes the class taking into account its ontological model. Notice how in Figure 3.12a, despite the low amount of axioms, the quality of the labels contributes to a description that is already comparable to human comments.

For this reason, we rely on a template as a baseline to compare the output generated using the Large Language Models. The template is fixed to

```
[CLASS LABEL] specialises [VERBALISED SUPERCLASSES]. [CLASS LABEL]
→ generalises [VERBALISED SUBCLASSES]. [CLASS LABEL] [RANGE
→ PROPERTIES]. [DOMAIN PROPERTIES] [CLASS LABEL].
```

The example of Figure 3.12a would hence result in

```
imitation margarine specialises member of some butter product
→ analog, derives from some oil-producing plant, butter product
→ analog.
```

while the example of Figure 3.12b would be

```
Role specialises classifies only Object, Concept, has part only
→ Role. has task a Task, is role defined in a Description, is
→ role of a Object. Task is task of Role, Object has role Role,
→ Description defines role Role.
```

3.4.4 Improving the comment through a LLM

To generate a coherent comment, we rely on a Large Language Model fed with the class descriptions extracted from the ontologies. We experiment with different prompts that encode increasing levels of detail relying on two techniques: zero-shot and few-shot prompting [99].

We provide 4 levels of details, that are described in Table 3.3. We test the zero-shot scenario by only relying on the first prompt of Table 3.3. While in principle we could test all the prompts in a zero-shot fashion, it has been shown that few-shot prompting outperforms zero-shot prompting in many different tasks [99]

For the few-show scenario, we include three examples of human-created comments for each prompt, alongside a class description verbalised according to the prompt. Finally, we provide the model with a sentence that describes how it will have to act. This prompting technique, sometimes referred to as *cloze* prompt [99], has proven its efficacy in obtaining results that highly resemble real-world human agents [100]. We use a fixed sentence for each prompt of Table 3.3:

```
I want you to act as an ontology design tutor. I will provide you
→ with classes of an ontology and information about them and you
→ will generate a comment of the class. Here are some examples of
→ classes and their comments:
```

For the zero-shot scenario, we simply remove the sentence where we state that some reference classes and comments will be provided.

We test each of the prompts of Table 3.3 against all the ontologies of Table 3.2 using three different open-source Large Language Models: Falcon²⁰, Llama 2 [101] and neural-chat²¹. Each model has been fine-tuned to follow human instructions and is composed of 7 billion of parameters. This allows our method to scale to big ontology without massive hardware requirements. Through the use of modern implementations, [102] and quantisation techniques [103] it is possible to use those models on a consumer-level machine. We run a total of 249 experiments. By relying on the statistics of Table 3.2, we only generate comments up to 150 words and we preemptively stop the generation when the model produces a sentence followed by a full stop. While we acknowledge that commenting a class using a single sentence is a strong assumption, we found that without any constraint the model tends to generate broken sentences and hallucinations [104]. This can be tackled by using bigger models, which have been shown to generate more coherent sentences [105]. Nonetheless, their resource requirements results in a method that is

²⁰<https://falconllm.tii.ae/>

²¹<https://huggingface.co/Intel/neural-chat-7b-v3-1>

Description	Example prompt
1 Only the class label	<pre>class: Role comment:</pre>
2 Specialisations and generalisations	<pre>concept: Role specializations: generalizations: classifies only Object, Concept, has part only Role, comment:</pre>
3 Relations to properties through domains and ranges	<pre>class: Role specializations: generalizations: classifies only Object, Concept, has part only Role, is domain of: has task a Task, is role defined in a Description, is role of a Object, is range of: Description defines role, Object has role, Task is task of, comment:</pre>
4 Explicit reference to OWL ontologies through RDFS	<pre>owl:class: Role rdfs:subClassOf: rdfs:domain: has task a Task, is role defined in a Description, is role of a Object, rdfs:range Description defines role, Object has role, Task is task of, rdfs:comment:</pre>

Table 3.3: Examples of the different levels of detail (first column) in each prompt, using the description of Figure 3.12b as an example. Notice that, as the the level of detail increases, new information are incrementally added to the ones of the previous level, except in the last prompt.

This happens since there is no explicit RDFS property to state the superclasses of an OWL class. We hence remove this information to avoid any confusion.

difficult to use in a common ontology engineering scenario, where high-performance resources are not always available.

4 Evaluation

In this chapter, we discuss the impact that RevOnt, IDEA+, EODPs and ontology documentation using LLM, as tools support for ontology engineering, are expected to have on the Semantic Web community. Moreover, we describe the steps that we are taking for the technical evaluation of the tool and a user-based evaluation as well in order to assess the quality of the tool and identify bugs and new feature requests.

4.1 The Evaluation of RevOnt's Performance to Generate CQs

This section describes the end-to-end evaluation of RevOnt, which encompasses its core components: verbalisation abstraction, question generalisation, and question filtering.

To systematically evaluate the output of RevOnt at different stages, we assembled a dataset of manually curated *verbalisations* and *competency questions* that were annotated from a subset of WDV (Section 4.1.1). The resulting annotations were then used as ground truth and compared to the RevOnt generations using BLEU – a metric for automatically evaluating machine-translated text.

The BLEU score is a number between zero and one that measures the similarity of the machine-translated text to a set of high-quality reference translations [106]. The annotations serve as grams, each with a weight of 0.5. The number of reference human translations influences the results. Usually, more references result in better and more accurate scores. According to [107] scores over 0.3 generally reflect understandable translations and scores over 0.5 reflect high quality translations (see Table 4.1 for an interpretation of BLEU scores). Intuitively, this allows to evaluate RevOnt's verbalisations and competency questions as alternative formulations (or valid translations) of their corresponding human annotations.

To complement the BLEU-based evaluation, we also compared syntactic properties of RevOnt-generated and human-annotated competency questions, and performed statistical tests to evaluate their significance (Section 4.1.3).

4.1.1 Dataset collection

To manually annotate verbalisation and competency questions from the WDV dataset (c.f. Section 3.1.1), we have collected data from $N = 15$ participants with an engineering background and familiar with ontology development. The participants are occupied mostly as ontology engineers, machine learning engineers, and data scientists. Their selection was primarily motivated by their familiarity with ontology development, especially the concept of competency questions and the

Table 4.1: Interpretation of BLEU scores

BLEU Score	Interpretation
< 0.10	Almost useless
0.10 - 0.19	Hard to get the gist
0.20 - 0.29	The gist is clear, but has significant errors
0.30 - 0.40	Understandable to good translations
0.40 - 0.50	High quality translations
0.50 - 0.60	Very high quality, adequate, and fluent translations
> 0.60	Quality often better than human

participants’ ability to formulate them as engineering requirements. Their task consisted in manually reproducing the stages of verbalisation abstraction and question generation. In total, we created 20 forms¹ (one per theme), with a varying number of properties. The properties, which were manually reproduced, were generated using 7.6K unique triples from WDV. The number of properties depends on the variety of triple verbalisations pertaining to a specific theme. Each theme falls within a domain encompassing the 20 most common types on Wikidata, ranging from written works, chemical compounds, and artists, to monuments, sport, and transportation (c.f. Table 4.2). Although all the WDV themes stem from Wikidata, these categories cover different domains and provide a reasonable level of diversity in terms of ontological requirements.

Given the nature of the tasks, no personal information was collected from the participants and minimal risk clearance was granted from the Research Ethics of King’s College London with registration number MRSP-22/23-34232.

First, we introduced the participants to the theme and the data that they need to complete the tasks. For each task, we provide the triple verbalisation, the subject, the subject description, the object, and the object description. The illustration used to describe the data is shown in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1: An illustration of example data including the triple verbalisation, the labels and descriptions of the subject and object of the triple. The example serves to explain the data needed to perform the tasks.

¹The forms and the full responses can be found here <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1M7LCmqw4dc33U73GTauec02h3JNnNxv4>

Table 4.2: An overview of the number of properties based on themes. The number of properties corresponds to the number of distinct properties of the triples of theme. The Task-Triple Ratio represents the proportion of properties relative to the triples within a specific theme.

Theme	Properties	Property-Triple Ratio
Airport	27	7.06%
Artist	65	16.92%
Astronaut	57	16.23%
Athlete	53	13.76%
Building	67	17.4%
Celestial body	25	6.49%
Chemical compound	33	8.61%
City	72	18.79%
Comics character	79	21.01%
Food	64	17.39%
Mean of transportation	58	15.42%
Monument	62	16.31%
Mountain	23	5.98%
Painting	29	7.53%
Politician	56	14.54%
Sports team	49	12.79%
Street	21	5.46%
Taxon	27	7.01%
University	62	16.4%
Written work	21	5.45%
Total	950	

Next, we used examples to describe the two tasks that they were required to carry out. The first task is to abstract a triple verbalisation given the information provided, shown in Figure 4.2. While the second task is to formulate questions based on the abstraction that they have created. Participants were asked to formulate three questions, where the answers to the questions would be 1) the subject of the abstraction, 2) the property, and 3) the object of the abstraction. The tasks are illustrated in Figure 4.3.

We arranged for each theme to be covered by two participants. In total, we have gathered 40 responses from the forms, containing approximately 1.9k annotations. Meanwhile, the WDV dataset has on average 380 triple verbalisations per theme. The coverage of each theme with annotations can be found in Table 4.2. We release our dataset as **WDV-CQ** and provide both the human-annotated and the RevOnt-generated verbalisations and competency questions as two distinct subsets: WDV-CQ-HA and WDV-CQ-RO, respectively. WDV-CQ provides 1786 manually annotated competency questions and 1904 verbalisation abstractions; The dataset can be

Figure 4.2: Example illustration for Task 1, describing the abstraction of a verbalisation using the given data. The abstraction is completed by generalising the subject and the object of the triple, and not the property.

Figure 4.3: Example illustration for Task 2, describing the generation of three questions when the answer is provided (either the subject, the property, or the object of a triple).

accessed from Zenodo² and is available under the Attribution 4.0 International (CC-BY 4.0) license.

4.1.2 Experimental results

In the following subsections, we report the results for each of the stages of RevOnt and summarise the results for the whole system. To interpret the distribution of the BLEU scores for the Verbalisation Abstraction and the Question Generation stage, we provide box and whisker plots.

²<https://zenodo.org/records/10370725>

A. Verbalisation Abstraction evaluation

The distribution of the BLEU scores for the Verbalisation Abstraction stage is presented in Figure 4.4. As seen from the plot, the median of the scores is 0.41, which is interpreted as a high quality translation. The 75th percentile is 0.55 and the 25th percentile is 0.3. Meanwhile, the highest and the lowest data points are respectively 1 and 0. These results mean that 75% of the abstractions generated from RevOnt have a good to high quality.

During a manual thorough examination of the abstractions generated by RevOnt, that are included in the experiment, and those created by the participants we noticed that the main difference between them is that the abstraction generated by RevOnt is more general. In most cases, the system abstracts the subject and the object of the verbalisation into more general classes than a user. As shown in Example 4.1, the system abstracts Michael Jackson as a human, while a user abstracts it as a singer.

Example 4.1.1. *The difference between the abstraction generated by RevOnt and by the users*

```
Verbalisation: Michael Jackson is a member of the
                Michael Jackson discography.
RevOnt:        Human is a member of the discography.
User annotation: A singer is a member of the discography.
```

B. Question generation evaluation

Figure 4.5 report the distribution of BLEU scores of RevOnt-generated CQs. The median is 0.3, which is close to being interpreted as a “good translation”. The 75th percentile is 0.47 and the 25th percentile is 0.21. The highest and the lowest data points are 0.81 and 0.1 respectively.

The non-satisfactory evaluation of this stage is explained in Figure 4.6. In this plot, we have evaluated individually the generation of each type of question. The red plot represents the generation of the questions when the answer is the subject of the abstraction, the yellow plot when the answer is the property of the triple, and the green plot when the answer is the object of the abstraction.

The generation of the question when the answer is the property of the triple performs poorly. This result backs the argument made in Section 3.1 where we hypothesise that the questions that T5 generates in this case are generally identical to the ones that it generates when the answer is the object of the abstraction. In Example 4.1.2, we show the difference between the question that is generated by RevOnt and by the user when the answer is the property of the triple.

Example 4.1.2. *The difference between the questions generated by RevOnt and the users when the answer is the property of the triple.*

```
Verbalisation: Michael Jackson is a member of the
                Michael Jackson discography.
```


Figure 4.4: Distribution of BLEU scores for the evaluation of the Verbalisation Abstraction module; considering all the domains/themes of the WDV dataset.

Figure 4.5: BLEU scores for the Question Generation stage. In the plot is shown the distribution of BLEU scores for the Question Generation stage for all the domains of the dataset including the three types of questions.

Answer: discography/member of
 RevOnt: What is a human a member of?
 User annotation: Which is the relation between a singer and the discography?

Comparing the scenarios when the subject and the object of the abstraction are the answer, we observe that the latter is more accurate with a median of 0.42, which is considered a high quality translation. The 75th percentile is 0.61, the 25th percentile 0.28, and the highest point is 1.0 and the lowest is 0.08. 75% of the scores for this category of questions is of good to high quality.

Figure 4.6: BLEU score for the Question Generation stage individualised. In the plot is shown the distribution of BLEU scores for each type of question that is produced by the Question Generation stage for all the domains of the dataset.

C. RevOnt 2-stage evaluation

The results of this evaluation provide further insights into the Question Generation stage. We expect a granular evaluation of the quality of each type of question to drive the refinement of the RevOnt framework. As mentioned earlier, the design choice to include all three types of questions is purely experimentation and to support future development.

Figure 4.7 reports a Box and Whisker plot of BLEU scores (generated against manually annotated questions) when RevOnt considers the *object* of the abstraction as the answer for Question Generation (which is the category of questions that performs the best). Overall, the BLEU scores for the system have a median of 0.4, which is considered as a good quality for language translation.

Figure 4.7: Distribution of BLEU scores for the RevOnt framework containing the Verbalisation Abstraction and the Question Generation stage with only one type of question (the question that is answered by the object of the triple).

D. Question filtering

The proposed model for question-based paraphrase detection was trained and evaluated on the Quora Question Pair (QPP) dataset [108], which contains 400k+ annotated records of the form (q_1, q_2, y) with $y \in \{0, 1\}$ (0 meaning different questions; 1 meaning equivalent questions). Given the size of the dataset, we use a static split to create the training, validation, and test sets.

Although the QPP dataset covers *questions* in the wider sense (e.g. “What is the difference between a neutral and border state?”), we expect a model trained on this dataset to transfer to *competency questions*. This is motivated by the less general and easier formulation of a competency question, which is supposed to lead to less ambiguity when attempting to classify its equivalence to an alternative formulation. Therefore, the QQP dataset can be considered as a challenging benchmark to train and evaluate our model.

Our model was trained to minimise the binary cross entropy loss between the predicted and the ground-truth labels. The model is implemented in `PyTorch` 1.12 and trained on a NVIDIA T4. An early stopping strategy is used to prevent overfitting with 15 epochs of patience. All dropout layers are set with a drop probability of 0.5 and a fixed learning rate of 0.001 is used by the Adam optimiser with default hyper-parameters ($\beta_1 = 0.9$, and $\beta_2 = 0.999$). A threshold of 0.5 is used to sample from the learned Bernoulli distribution at the sigmoid layer (e.g. the model outputs $\hat{y} \leq 0.5$ as 0, meaning that the given questions are not equivalent; and $\hat{y} > 0.5$ as 1, in case of equivalence). This is only needed for measuring the model's accuracy on the test set. Notably, we did not find class imbalance in QPP; hence, we can rely on the model's accuracy as the main metric for evaluation.

After ten epochs, training stops with a test loss of 0.32 and accuracy above 86%, which is comparable to the classification results of [108]. The trained model can effectively identify redundant sentences, encompassing both identical sentences and semantically similar ones. For instance, multiple redundant competency questions may convey the same meaning with varied structures, such as “What is the genre of Comics?” and “Comics is in what genre?”. In sum, our model can streamline the set of competency questions by eliminating semantically identical sentences.

4.1.3 Syntactic analysis of verbalisations and CQs

To evaluate and compare qualitative properties of competency questions and verbalisation abstractions, we extracted a set of metrics from the WDV-CQ dataset, and compared their distributions between the human-annotated (WDV-CQ-HA) and the RevOnt-generated (WDV-CQ-RO) subsets. This was done by computing sentence-level features on each subset, individually, and performing statistical tests between both groups to detect significant differences. The evaluation is based on two groups of features: *frequency-based* and *statistic-based*. The first group includes features related to the count of words, verbs, nouns, adjectives, pronouns, etc. The second group include readability features, such as the Flesch-Kincaid grade, the Coleman-Liau test, and the Automated Readability index. We decided to include 6 different readability features as their formulation is designed for different applications (labelling technical manuals, supporting high-tech education, etc.), although they measure readability by approximating the US grade level needed

to comprehend a given text. Here, their complementary formulation is needed as there is no universal definition of readability. Together with the frequency-based features, we expect readability scores and syntactic properties to describe structural properties of competency questions and verbalisation abstractions; whose span always corresponds to a single sentence. All features are outlined in Table 4.3.

The distributions of each measure per subset are illustrated in Figures 4.8 and 4.9 for both frequency-based and statistics-based features, respectively. To detect statistical differences between subsets (WDV-CQ-HA and WDV-CQ-RO), we performed pairwise Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) tests on each feature. KS tests were chosen due to their non-parametric nature, making them suitable when the normality assumption of the input distributions under comparison is violated (as visible from the skewed distributions plotted in Figures 4.8 and 4.9). The results of the statistical tests are provided in the Appendix (Tables 4 and 5), along with the mean and the standard deviation of each feature per subset.

Overall, the boxplots in Figure 4.8 reveal similarities of features across the human-annotated (HA) and the RevOnt-generated (RO) subsets for Verbalisation, SubjectCQ, and ObjectCQ. In contrast, the boxplots for PropertyCQ differ considerably, displaying high variance and skewness for RO features. The same can be observed for the statistics-based features (readability scores) in Figure 4.9.

On average, when looking at the verbalisations, RO produces slightly longer sentences compared to those in HA (9.10 ± 3.78 and 9.10 ± 3.78 words, respectively); whereas their number of verbs is quite similar (1.23 ± 0.67 and 1.36 ± 0.67). We also observe strong similarities for the number of adverbs, adjectives, pronouns, conjunctions, and modal verbs – which are all close to 0; as well as for adjectives and prepositions (close to 1 for both subsets). This implies that RevOnt manages to approximate the syntactic structure of a well-defined (human-annotated) verbalisation. Instead, the slight increase in length of RO's verbalisations could be associated to the higher number of nouns (HA : 3.28 ± 1.83 ; RO: 4.93 ± 2.85) and named entities (HA : 0.46 ± 0.89 ; RO: 2.05 ± 1.16) generated by RevOnt. Concerning the statistics-based features, Figure 4.9 confirms that while readability scores (US grade levels) returned by the various tests have different magnitudes; they all grow consistently with respect to the subsets (RO and HA scores are directly proportional). Therefore, rather than attempting to map our verbalisations to the required US grade levels, we can still observe that RevOnt's verbalisations have a tendency to be more complex to read. For example, the average Flesch-Kincaid scores for HA and RO are 5.16 ± 4.30 and 6.82 ± 5.81 , respectively.

In line with the experimental setup of Section 4.1.2, we performed the syntactic analysis of competency questions individually on those defined from subjects (SubjectCQ), predicates (PropertyCQ), and objects (ObjectCQ). The results revealed similar insights to the verbalisations. Frequency-based features related to the count of words, verbs, and nouns have comparable distributions across HA and RO; with adjectives, adverbs, pronouns occurring rarely in both subsets. Overall, CQs originating from predicates (PropertyCQ) are the longest for human-annotators (HA), with a higher number of nouns, conjunctions, and unique words. Instead, RevOnt shows the opposite trend, as the same features have the lowest figures in comparison to SubjectCQ and

Figure 4.8: Comparison of frequency-based features between human-annotated (WDV-CQ-HA) and RevOnt-generated (WDV-CQ-RO) verbalisation sand CQs, on a log scale.

ObjectCQ. This is also confirmed by the readability scores in Figure 4.9, which are considerably high for HA (Flesch-Kincaid grade of 6.04 ± 4.17) while being lower yet with higher variability for RO (Flesch Kincaid grade 1.15 ± 7.17). We hypothesise that the inverted trend is due to the nature of the task, as human participants found the formulation of CQs from the predicate to be less intuitive; which in turn, could explain the lengthier and more complex HA competency questions. Instead, RevOnt tends to produce shorter and simpler questions from the triple’s predicate.

Figure 4.9: Comparison of statistics-based features (readability measures) between human-annotated (WDV-CQ-HA) and RevOnt-generated (WDV-CQ-RO) verbalisations and CQs.

However, the latter yielded the lowest BLEU scores in relation to the human annotations (c.f. Section 4.1.2), meaning that their output is not accurate.

For SubjectCQs, HA competency questions are the easiest to read (e.g. Flesh-Kincaid score: 2.22 ± 4.21), whereas RevOnt produces more complex CQs (e.g. Flesh-Kincaid score: 3.99 ± 3.42). The most alignment among both subsets is observed for ObjectCQ, which produces the smallest differences for both frequency-based and statistics-based features. This finding rein-

forces the results reported Section 4.1.2, where RevOnt attained the best BLEU scores for the competency question generation module. This implies that not only the CQs extracted from (triple) objects are the most accurate semantically (i.e., they entail similar ontological requirements when compared to human-generated CQs), but they also have similar syntactic properties. To shed more light into the latter finding, Table 4.4 provides comparative examples between HA and RO. It reveals a distinct difference: HA typically employs more abstract and general words, whereas RO still makes extensive use of named entities, such as “Leo” or “Michael J Adams”. For ‘SubjectCQ’, the structure of the competency questions is similar; however, RO often incorporates specific named entities into the generation of CQs, forming simpler structured sentences than those found in HA. This is confirmed by the statistical tests, have indicated potential significant differences between WDV-CQ and RevOnt-CQ, which may be attributed to the use of named-entity words. Nevertheless, CQs generated by HA and RO show similarities. Therefore, reducing the reliance on named-entity words could be a key factor in enhancing the quality of RO-generated CQs.

Table 4.3: Overview of the features used to describe and compare qualitative properties of competency questions and verbalisation abstraction. Features are grouped into *frequency-based* and *statistics-based*, with the latter entailing readability properties.

Group	Feature	Description
Frequency-based	word count	Number of words
	verb count	Number of verbs
	noun count	Number of nouns
	adj count	Number of adjectives
	adv count	Number of adverbs
	pron count	Number of pronouns
	conj count	Number of conjunctions
	prep count	Number of prepositions
	modal verb count	Number of modal verbs (could, should, would, etc.)
	unique word count	Number of distinct words
	stop word count	Number of commonly used stop words, e.g. “the”, “is”, “in”, etc.
NE count	Number of named entities (e.g. persons, organizations, locations, etc.)	
Statistic-based	Flesch Kincaid grade	A readability score that approximates the U.S. grade level thought necessary to comprehend the text. It ranges from 0-1 (Pre-kindergarten - 1st grade) to 11-18 (11th grade - 18th grade).
	Coleman Liau index	A test designed to gauge the understandability of a text, which also approximates the U.S. grade level but relies on characters instead of syllables per word. It is computed by accounting for the proportion of letters and sentences per 100 words.
	Automated Readability Index	Another approximate of readability in relation to the required US grade level, which also relies on character statistics. The index was designed for real-time monitoring of readability on electric typewriters.
	Dale Chall Readability	A readability formula based on a list of 3000 familiar words that groups of fourth-grade American students could reliably understand. The formula considers any word not on that list to be difficult.
	Linsear Write	Another approximation of US grade level, based on sentence length and the number of words with 3+ syllables. It was originally developed to compute the readability of US Air Force technical manuals.
	Gunning Fog	A readability test calculating a weighted average of the number of words per sentence, and the number of long words per sentence.

Table 4.4: Examples of human-annotated (HA) and RevOnt-generated (RO) competency questions from the WDV-CQ dataset.

Subset	Original statement	subjectCQ	propertyCQ	objectCQ
<i>Good examples</i>				
RO	Klaus Francke's catalog code is 11000569.	Whose catalog code is 11000569?	What is Klaus Francke's?	What is Klaus Francke's catalog code?
HA	-	Who has the catalog code 11000569?	What does Klaus Francke has?	What is the catalog code of Klaus Francke
<i>Modest examples</i>				
RO	Zach Trotman has 13 career points.	Who has 13 career points?	How many career points does Zach Trotman have?	How many career points does Zach Trotman have?
HA	-	Who has 13 career points?	What is the connection between American ice hockey defenceman and the 13 career ponits?	How many career points does American ice hockey defenceman have?
<i>Bad examples</i>				
RO	Kirk Muller has 357 goals in his career.	Who has 357 goals in his career?	How many goals has Kirk Muller scored?	How many goals has Kirk Muller scored in his career?
HA	-	Who has 357 goals in his career?	What does Canadian ice hockey player have to do with 357 goals?	How many goals does Canadian ice hockey player have?

4.2 Examples of The IDEA+ Framework Implementation

The LLM-powered IDEA+ framework is a challenging topic, currently lacking a definitive method for its evaluation. As a result, we have developed a simple interface and prototype to assess its potential advantages, using examples for each component. Initially, we created a straightforward form for interactive story generation between the user and the LLM, as shown in Figure 4.10. This form consists of three parts: persona specification, Goal/Requirements Specification, and Example Specification, which together initiate the user story generation process. In the persona specification part, the LLM gains a general understanding of the user's background and domain. This understanding aids the LLM in tailoring the generated user story. Subsequently, the user provides goal and requirements specifications. Given that these specifications are abstract, users must also provide examples to enable the LLM to write a detailed user story. After completing these three parts, the LLM drafts the user story. Finally, through the implemented interface, users can interact with the LLM to refine the user story.

We conducted a simple user story creation evaluation involving three experts, each tasked with creating a distinct user story in the music domain, supported by the LLM. The results demonstrated that the model successfully captured the specified requirements and user goals in a well-structured user story. Additionally, it was noted that the model significantly reduced the time required for user story creation. However, there is a recognition that further exploration is needed in the area of example data generation. It was also observed that while hallucinations produced by the model can be useful, they sometimes have the potential to be distracting or even irritating. We tested the LLM's capability for extracting CQs using a simple user story, as illustrated in Figure 4.11. The user story revolves around the song 'Let it be' by 'The Beatles' and its chord sequence. Initially, the LLM generated a CQ that was accurate yet too specific. Through a multiple CQs checking process, we derived three CQs from the LLM. These CQs appeared to be effective, as they successfully tested aspects like the song title, the singer, and the chords used. Finally, after undergoing a process called named entity substitution, the CQs became more simplified and generalized.

In Figure 4.12, we demonstrate an example of extracting examples using the capabilities of the LLM. We provided the LLM with a simple CQ: 'Who composed the song?'. In response, the LLM generated clear, yet straightforward examples relevant to the CQ. Furthermore, the LLM is capable of creating more specific examples by identifying general concepts and substituting them with named entities from the real world. This example illustrates that if we have a sufficient repository of named entities or individuals for ontology creation, generating domain-specific examples becomes significantly easier with the assistance of the LLM.

In Figure 4.13, we present our test of the SPARQL-free ontology testing method. For this test, we chose the Music Meta Ontology of Polifonia. Initially, we serialized the ontology to prepare it for input to the LLM. Following this, the LLM verbalized the serialized ontology using a specially designed instruction prompt. The LLM then tested the ontology with the verbalized text and generated CQs, all without any use of SPARQL. The LLM was successful in testing parts of the ontology, such as identifying subjects or objects, but occasionally failed in testing relationships.

Figure 4.10: Interactive user story generation process with the help of LLM by obtaining the concept of persona, goal, and examples

For instance, the LLM struggled to accurately test the CQ 'What is the relationship between a creative process and the music entity it creates?'. This suggests that the LLM might find it challenging to understand overly abstract concepts related to relationships.

Figure 4.11: A process of competency questions generation with the LLM based on the generated user story

Figure 4.12: An example of named entity recognition for generated CQs

Figure 4.13: SPARQL-free ontology validation for serialized ontology documents with LLMs

4.3 Evaluation of automatic ontology documentation

The generated are evaluated comments by comparing them to human-written ones. We rely upon measures developed in the Natural Language Processing (NLP) field to compare two sentences. In particular, we compute the ROUGE [109], METEOR [110], BERT score [111], chrF [112], chrF+ and chrF++ scores [113]. Informally, ROUGE and chrF-based scores compare comments based on the exact words used. Higher scores mean higher similarity in a token-based sense: the more two comments share some terms, the higher the score. On the other hand, METEOR and BERT compare comments in a sentence-based sense. Both models are based on neural networks that are trained to predict how similar pairs of sentences are regardless of the tokens they are composed of. They are hence supposed to take into account the semantics of the sentence. Note that even though this seems the optimal evaluation approach, both metrics are usually trained on standard NLP tasks, such as machine translation or summarisation [111]. The produced score may be over-confident in the quality of the generated comments since in the context of the original task it would be a quality sentence. Designing metrics to compute the quality of the generated text is a notably hard task in a very active research field [114]. We will hence provide some qualitative examples of the results to showcase good and bad generated comments.

In Table 4.5 the results of the experiments of Section 4 are reported. Using a LLM largely outperforms the template-based approach on any ontology. Interestingly, by looking at the BERT score on the HeLiS ontology, the baseline performs better than other methods. As already stated in Section 4, some results from the metrics might be misleading. Indeed, by looking at other other metrics on the same ontology, LLMs perform largely better. Overall, Falcon seems to be the most suited model to solve the task. It outperforms the other models in half of the datasets we tested.

4.3.1 Prompting the right way

In Table 4.6 we report the influence of *cloze* prompting (as explained in Section 3). Generally, the performances significantly increase when the LLM is instructed to be an expert ontology engineer. This aligns with other results from the literature [99, 100]. Notably, it seems that the amount of information provided by Prompt 3, which encodes more information than all the other prompts, does not directly result in an accuracy improvement. On the other hand, making RDF syntax explicit, as done in Prompt 4, results in the best prompt overall.

In Table 4.7 we report some generated comments compared with the human-made one and the verbalisation baseline. As stated in Section 1, one of the major issues of using a traditional verbalisation method to comment a class is that there is no guarantee that the class will have an extensive axiomatisation. Indeed, we can see from Table 4.7 that the comment provided by the baseline is not informative at all. On the contrary, the ones provided by the language model can be used as a draft and eventually further enhanced. It needs to be noted, however, that not all the prompts behave equally well. For instance, the comment provided by Prompt 4, the best prompt on aggregate as shown in Table 4.6, completely misses the point of describing the class.

Ontology	LLM	BERT	METEOR	Rouge	chrF	chrF+	chrF++
Arco	Baseline	0.83	0.16	0.14	24.94	23.87	21.34
	Neural Chat	0.86	0.27	0.26	29.75	29.98	28.06
	LLAMAv2	0.85	0.20	0.19	25.64	25.39	23.18
	Falcon	0.86	0.32	0.29	33.71	33.89	32.12
DBPedia	Baseline	0.76	0.10	0.12	17.89	17.08	15.14
	Neural Chat	0.83	0.21	0.19	24.00	24.02	22.34
	LLAMAv2	0.81	0.20	0.20	22.90	22.91	21.43
	Falcon	0.84	0.25	0.24	27.58	27.67	26.07
DOLCE	Baseline	0.83	0.10	0.09	17.03	16.44	14.46
	Neural Chat	0.86	0.33	0.31	34.33	34.51	32.87
	LLAMAv2	0.84	0.25	0.25	26.61	26.89	25.37
	Falcon	0.86	0.26	0.25	29.15	29.19	27.45
FoodOn	Baseline	0.78	0.05	0.05	8.18	8.00	7.13
	Neural Chat	0.84	0.30	0.28	31.52	31.49	30.04
	LLAMAv2	0.85	0.24	0.24	28.21	28.18	26.33
	Falcon	0.84	0.24	0.23	27.01	26.91	25.25
FRBR	Baseline	0.80	0.07	0.09	15.38	14.69	12.86
	Neural Chat	0.83	0.29	0.26	29.20	29.36	27.64
	LLAMAv2	0.86	0.31	0.29	32.96	33.23	31.38
	Falcon	0.83	0.23	0.22	25.76	25.84	24.07
GO	Baseline	0.24	0.01	0.01	1.44	1.56	1.36
	Neural Chat	0.81	0.17	0.15	18.82	19.06	17.49
	LLAMAv2	0.85	0.28	0.27	30.46	30.53	28.83
	Falcon	0.86	0.35	0.33	36.01	36.13	34.31
Helis	Baseline	0.86	0.20	0.25	23.04	24.04	22.11
	Neural Chat	0.85	0.32	0.31	31.85	32.18	30.76
	LLAMAv2	0.84	0.27	0.26	30.85	30.71	28.99
	Falcon	0.81	0.18	0.17	21.67	21.44	19.78
Schema.org	Baseline	0.84	0.07	0.03	12.77	12.87	11.26
	Neural Chat	0.81	0.17	0.15	20.87	21.01	19.01
	LLAMAv2	0.84	0.21	0.20	23.84	23.89	22.22
	Falcon	0.86	0.30	0.28	31.30	31.55	29.84

Table 4.5: Results of the generation method on the ontologies of table 3.2. The best results are represented in bold.

4.3.2 Are generated comments reliable?

While the results of Table 4.5 provide a clear indication that using a LLM to generate comments is quantitatively better than a straightforward verbalisation approach, it is difficult to distinguish

Prompt	Instruction tuning sentence	μ (metrics)
Zero-shot		12.76
Zero-shot	✓	15.73 (+23%)
Prompt 1		12.78
Prompt 1	✓	14.78 (+15.64%)
Prompt 2		14.48
Prompt 2	✓	14.23 (-1.72%)
Prompt 3		11.79
Prompt 3	✓	12.28 (+4.15%)
Prompt 4		14.06
Prompt 4	✓	17.11 (+21.79%)

Table 4.6: Performance of each of the prompts defined in Table 3.3. μ (metrics) is computed by averaging all the metrics related to a specific prompt.

Model	Comment
Human made	Color or colour is the visual perceptual property corresponding in humans to the categories called red, yellow, blue and others. Color derives from the spectrum of light (distribution of light energy versus wavelength) interacting in the eye with the spectral sensitivities of the light receptors.
Baseline	colour generalises Thing.
Zero-shot	This is a comment
Prompt 1	a colour is a particular shade or hue.
✓ Prompt 1	a colour is a visual attribute of an object or animal.
Prompt 2	colour is a visual attribute of an object or thing.
✓ Prompt 2	colour is a property of an object that can be observed and measured.
Prompt 3	<i>No comment provided</i>
✓ Prompt 3	colour is a property of a thing that can be observed and measured.
Prompt 4	a colour is a visual perception of a colour or the appearance of an object or person.
✓ Prompt 4	The comment of the class is a description of the class and its range.

Table 4.7: Examples of comments compiled for the color entity of DBpedia. The checkmark (✓) in front of a name states that it is using the instruction tuned prompt.

the effectiveness of each model.

In Figure 4.14 we report some statistics computed from the data of Table 4.5. In particular, we compute how much longer (or shorter) each generated comment is compared to the real one and how stable are the metrics of Table 4.5. We find that in some ontologies, particularly DOLCE, it is particularly difficult to match the length of the human-made comment. This is because of the nature of the ontology. A foundational ontology is supposed to encode comprehensive semantics that is expressed through the use of simple terms (e.g. *Role* in Figure 3.12b). Documenting this

Figure 4.14: Figure a displays the mean difference of words between the human and automatically generated comments for each model in each dataset. A value < 0 (resp. > 0) means that the generated comment is longer (resp. shorter) than the human one. Figure b we compute the standard deviations of the results aggregating by model and dataset. The lower the more stable the quality of generated comments is.

kind of ontologies means understanding their philosophical commitments. A comment needs to completely address the scope of the class analysed [55] and this is simply not possible in a few words when it comes to such ontologies. On the contrary, We can see that most models perform better in ontologies that analyse a specific domain, such as FRBR (bibliographical domain) or GO (biological domain).

5 Conclusions

This deliverable document demonstrated how the use of natural language processing and LLM methods enables the extraction of competency questions from knowledge graphs. The current implementation of RevOnt is publicly available on GitHub¹ and includes setup scripts and instructions to replicate all the steps of extraction process (c.f. Section 3.1). All code is released under the MIT license, whereas the WDV-CQ dataset follows the Attribution 4.0 International (CC-BY 4.0).

To use RevOnt, users are required to produce a verbalisation of their knowledge graph using the same format of the WDV dataset (as shown in the example in Figure 3.2). This ensures that the question generation module produces reliable results as reported in our experiments. Nonetheless, given the modular architecture of RevOnt, users can also redefine or implement their own question generation model (e.g. using an alternative verbalisation format) and plug its outputs in the question filtering module. By doing so, we expect the hyper-parameters of the methods and tools outlined in Table 3.1 to remain consistent with our experimental setup. Furthermore, IDEA+ is capable of reducing the gap between domain experts and ontology engineers by leveraging the power of the LLM. Through several simple examples, we have observed that the LLM holds significant potential to simplify and accelerate the ontology engineering process. EODPs extracted various types of ontology design patterns centered around specific themes from KGs. In particular, they included interpretations of extensive class trees and schemas related to the music domain. Through frequency-based class-to-class (or entities) relationship evaluations, the ontology design patterns extracted were analyzed for their coverage of practical entities they could encompass. This analysis aimed to assess how much actual Wikidata EODPs could incorporate. The performance of ontology documentation using LLM showed sufficient competitiveness compared to comments generated by humans. For this comparison, word count difference and score standard deviation were utilized to compare human-generated comments and model-generated comments for each dataset. As a result, in specific fields such as bibliographical and biological, the performance of ontology documentation using LLM was highly superior, while for other domains, it generated comments with somewhat lower specifications.

Limitations. Overall, workflows based on language models are notoriously sensitive to the input data and the configuration of the hyper-parameters [107]. This issue is generally observed in the generation of the questions by RevOnt and IDEA+, where the distance between the triple and its verbalisation plays a significant role (c.f. Example 4.1.2). In addition, language models are still prone to issues and limitations which inevitably propagate into RevOnt's pipeline. Below we highlight issues that are well-known at the intersection of natural language processing, ontology learning, and schema induction and discovery.

¹<https://github.com/King-s-Knowledge-Graph-Lab/revont>

1. In curating the WDV dataset, [71] already found that existing NER models performed poorly on specific themes (50% of the WDV dataset). Their performance is explained by the heterogeneous data used to train these models, which is comprehensively different compared to the dataset. These models are often trained with data from news articles, and email-s/chat data, which explains the good performance with themes such as Artist, Athlete, City, etc. By training a NER model with data specific to the domain of interest, it is possible to make the approach independent from the Wikidata query service.
2. In relation to the previous point, the verbalisation abstraction process in RevOnt (c.f. Section 3.1.2) has still a tendency to keep named entities. In fact, the distributions of NER counts for abstracted verbalisation and competency questions (Tables 4 and 5) have means greater than those observed for the human annotations. This can also be observed in the examples reported in Table 4.4. Identifying the correct abstraction for a given entity – depending on the context in which it occurs – is indeed a difficult task; especially when the context is poor (e.g. a single triple, rather than a paragraph of which the sentence is part of) or ambiguous ('Michael Jackson' as either a singer, musician, or person). By leveraging additional information extracted from the knowledge graph (e.g. a cluster of similar entities and relations) we expect a larger context to be more informative for abstracting named entities.
3. Generally, the default language of the training data of a language model is English, which limits the usability of the model for multilingual data. Big knowledge graphs such as Wikidata and DBpedia contain structured knowledge of entities in several distinct languages, and they are useful resources for cross-lingual artificial intelligence and natural language processing applications [115]. Therefore, language models trained with multilingual data could enhance the performance of the approach. An example of a multilingual language model is a release of BERT² that is pre-trained on the 104 languages with the largest Wikipedia pages. Another example is T5-base³, which covers English, French, Romanian, German [116].
4. The dependency between the language models and methods used in NLP pipelines may also pose further issues. As the overall performance of the system is impacted by each component, the effect of errors is multiplicative. This is due to the dependency of each component on the preceding, propagating errors along the processing. In the worst cases, this may result in a final output that may be unsatisfactory despite the good performance of each component, individually [117]. In RevOnt, this has been mitigated by finding a configuration of the models (Table 3.1) that is optimal to the tasks and the data at hand. Hence, extending or replacing one or more components would necessitate a trial and error approach to adjust the parametrisation of our methods.
5. IDEA+ heavily relies on the capabilities of the LLM, which can sometimes suffer from the problem of hallucination. Generally, ontology engineering involves the issue of ambiguity in defining classes, properties, etc. This ambiguity can exacerbate the LLM's hallucination,

²<https://huggingface.co/bert-base-multilingual-cased>

³<https://huggingface.co/t5-base>

necessitating the implementation of disambiguation processes and multiple validations to mitigate these effects.

6. A set of examples is a crucial component for testing the constraints and rules defined in an ontology. However, the LLM is not adept at generating numerical or specific data values, such as height or the number of parts. To facilitate more concrete and complete example generation, IDEA+ should incorporate other predictive models that are specialized in numerical reasoning or regression predictions.

Overall, a way to mitigate the aforementioned issues is the addition of a manual validation phase across the various steps; where end-users can collaboratively refine the outputs of the system. This may be facilitated by interactive interfaces as well as crowd-sourcing and social media approaches to validate the intermediate results [33]. Notably, most of the issues arise from known limitations of NLP methods, especially when applied to novel or unconventional uses cases such as the one proposed in this article. Given the latest developments in NLP, we believe that most of these concerns can effectively be addressed by Large Language Models and Conversational AI systems such as ChatGPT⁴, and Bard⁵, which we expect to further improve the results reported in this deliverable.

Future work. Based on the discussion above, and the opportunities opened up by RevOnt, we have also identified three directions that we plan to pursue as future work.

1. The method that we have defined generates questions based on the abstraction of triple verbalisations. In particular, the question generation model (T5) performs better when it is provided with the sentence and the answer. This limits the usability of the method with datasets where the answer is not explicit. It requires additional steps such as Part-Of-Speech tagging, parsing, and lemmatisation to be able to provide an entity as an answer. We plan to refine this aspect of the method by 1) detecting entities that might serve as answers 2) providing paragraphs instead of sentences. Concerning the second point, the T-Rex dataset is a good fit, since it provides textual descriptions of Wikidata entries. Related to this, we also plan to experiment with other language models and use KGs other than Wikidata to generalise our results.
2. As conceptualised in Figure 1.1, developing automatic or assisted workflows for ontology testing is also a planned research direction. One way to address this is to leverage large datasets of annotated CQs, e.g. the BigCQ dataset [118], to learn a mapping from competency questions to SPARQL templates. This would ensure that the generated CQs can be easily converted into SPARQL queries (for ontology testing and information retrieval) while providing methods for evaluating the potential reuse of a KG resource [119].
3. We also plan to extend the question generation module to handle the automatic creation, or induction, of competency questions corresponding to more than a single triple pattern. This would allow users to extract more complex ontological requirements, beyond those emerging from a local triple-level approach. Furthermore, there are a bunch of datasets of real-world queries that are more complicated and diverse, including SPARQL queries.

⁴<https://openai.com/blog/chatgpt>

⁵<https://bard.google.com>

We plan to include these datasets to improve RevOnt and evaluate the RevOnt framework from the perspective of real-world applications. Furthermore, we plan to investigate the capabilities of very large LLMs like GPT-4 and fine-tuned LMs in ontology engineering.

4. We have enhanced the IDEA+ framework by integrating machine learning techniques to address the hallucination problem inherent in the LLM. Additionally, we plan to conduct a comprehensive evaluation of the IDEA+ framework. This will enable us to better understand the potential of the LLM in ontology engineering and its weaknesses. Furthermore, we have developed a simple interface that integrates the LLM APIs with existing ontology engineering tools, making the framework more practical and user-friendly for real-world applications.

6 Compliance to FAIR principles

The following outputs have been released as a result of the work described in this deliverable:

- RevOnt software¹: This is an automatic CQs generation software, including Wikidata query requests, KGs verbalization with pre-trained models, and clustering for CQ reduction.
- WDV-CQ dataset²: It contains human-generated CQs for the verbalized WDV dataset extracted from Wikidata, comprising CQs for subjects, properties, and objects in RDF triples.
- IDEA+ interface³: This interface offers web-based interactive user story and CQs generation via conversation functionality based on the LLM (e.g., GPT-3.5).

This section encompasses information which helps to the knowledge management in the project and to make Polifonia FAIR (operating according to principles of Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable).

This ensures compliance with the guidelines and principles of the Polifonia Data Management Plan (v2.0) [120]. We remind the Polifonia 10 Rules for Open Science from D7.2 [120] as follows.

- R1: Polifonia requires that all essential components of the Polifonia Ecosystem are registered in the Polifonia Github community.
- R2: Polifonia recommends to use Zenodo to register output.
- R3: Organise access to your resources via the Polifonia Portal/Polifonia server.
- R4: Use your ORCID to identify you as an author!
- R5: Acknowledge the grant (the Polifonia project) with each output!
- R6: Use DOI's to refer to work you produce!
- R7: For datasets you think are important cornerstones of your work deposit them into the Polifonia Ecosystem (see R1). Consider archiving 'authoritative versions' into a certified data repository!
- R8: Authorship/publication Netiquette
- R9: R9: Adhere FAIR principles and licencing principles
- R10: If in doubt: Ask the DataManagers of your institutions and consult the DataStewards of Polifonia.

6.1 RevOnt – Software

¹<https://github.com/King-s-Knowledge-Graph-Lab/revont>

²https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-19433-7_32

³<https://github.com/King-s-Knowledge-Graph-Lab/OntoChat>

Requirement	Options	Outcome
Polifonia 10 Rules	None, R1, R2, ... , R10	R1, R5, R6, R8, R9
GitHub link	None, Link	https://github.com/King-s-Knowledge-Graph-Lab/revont
Ecosystem integration	Yes, Planned, N/A	Yes, see https://github.com/polifonia-project/pon-template
PON Alignment	Full, Partial, Planned, N/A	Full
License	License	CC-BY-4.0 (all modules)

Table 6.1: Overview of FAIRness coverage for RevOnt

6.2 WDV-CQ – Data

Requirement	Options	Outcome
Polifonia 10 Rules	None, R1, R2, ... , R10	R1, R2, R4, R5, R6, R8, R9
Zenodo link	None, Link	https://zenodo.org/records/10370725
Ecosystem integration	Yes, Planned, N/A	Yes, see https://github.com/polifonia-project/pon-template
PON Alignment	Full, Partial, Planned, N/A	Full
License	License	CC-BY-4.0 (all modules)
Deployment link	Link, N/A, Planned	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-19433-7_32

Table 6.2: Overview of FAIRness coverage for WDV-CQ

6.3 IDEA+ – Software

Requirement	Options	Outcome
Polifonia 10 Rules	None, R1, R2, ... , R10	R1, R5, R6, R8, R9
GitHub link	None, Link	https://github.com/King-s-Knowledge-Graph-Lab/OntoChat
Ecosystem integration	Yes, Planned, N/A	Yes, see https://github.com/polifonia-project/pon-template
PON Alignment	Full, Partial, Planned, N/A	Full
License	License	CC-BY-4.0 (all modules)

Table 6.3: Overview of FAIRness coverage for IDEA+

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Appendix

Table 4: Overview of aggregated *frequency-based* features extracted from human-annotated (WDV-CQ-HA subset) and RevOnt-generated (WDV-CQ-RO subset) verbalisations and competency questions. Mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ) are reported for each feature and subset, alongside the results of the statistical comparison across the distributions of the former groups.

Type	Feature	WDV-CQ-HA		WDV-CQ-RO		Statistical test	
		μ	σ	μ	σ	KS Statistic	p-value
Verbalisation	Word_count	9.10982	3.787903	11.174313	5.303054	0.1564	< 0.001
	Verb_count	1.239176	0.676624	1.366373	0.675432	0.0709	< 0.001
	Noun_count	3.284055	1.835723	4.932694	2.858977	0.3595	< 0.001
	Adj_count	0.659451	0.836106	0.619955	0.920612	0.0390	0.1352
	Adv_count	0.024815	0.158961	0.024583	0.161509	-	-
	Pron_count	0.007392	0.08568	0.017221	0.135061	-	-
	Conj_count	0.053326	0.238429	0.08926	0.327621	-	-
	Prep_count	0.998416	0.917919	1.151308	0.911466	0.1106	< 0.001
	Modal_verb_count	0.00264	0.051326	0.002235	0.047224	-	-
	Unique_word_count	8.520063	3.342623	10.491652	3.861173	0.2159	< 0.001
	Stop_word_count	2.92397	1.618542	2.893651	1.530433	0.0685	< 0.001
Ner_count	0.464097	0.894622	2.055475	1.165087	0.6488	< 0.001	
SubjectCQ	Word_count	7.461457	2.809941	9.397923	3.047233	0.2213	< 0.001
	Verb_count	1.250792	0.624332	1.386881	0.627028	0.0713	< 0.001
	Noun_count	2.133052	1.301077	2.853556	1.573297	0.1839	< 0.001
	Adj_count	0.388596	0.619286	0.382674	0.619288	0.0069	1
	Adv_count	0.022175	0.150836	0.011174	0.108809	-	-
	Pron_count	0.003696	0.060697	0.012488	0.112237	-	-
	Conj_count	0.029567	0.175559	0.022479	0.151752	-	-
	Prep_count	0.790919	0.745192	1.120547	0.71831	0.2038	< 0.001
	Modal_verb_count	0.003168	0.05621	0.001972	0.044365	-	-
	Unique_word_count	7.217529	2.585299	8.825292	2.354825	0.2441	< 0.001
	Stop_word_count	2.684794	1.399725	3.491784	1.841941	0.1689	< 0.001
Ner_count	0.230201	0.534905	0.644275	0.690399	0.3595	< 0.001	
PropertyCQ	Word_count	11.3717	4.290453	6.929539	3.610875	0.6247	< 0.001
	Verb_count	1.051742	0.506132	1.108321	0.634981	0.1078	< 0.001
	Noun_count	3.542239	1.902833	2.462732	1.633899	0.3193	< 0.001
	Adj_count	0.458289	0.707743	0.208492	0.471001	0.1708	< 0.001
	Adv_count	0.009504	0.097048	0.009728	0.098156	-	-
	Pron_count	0.00528	0.07249	0.005653	0.078405	-	-
	Conj_count	0.80887	0.46585	0.018667	0.135355	-	-
	Prep_count	1.222809	0.873382	0.509531	0.688841	0.4616	< 0.001
	Modal_verb_count	0.00264	0.051326	0.001446	0.038002	-	-
	Unique_word_count	10.57075	3.799798	6.741422	3.378023	0.6150	< 0.001
	Stop_word_count	5.181098	2.047106	1.995662	1.552773	0.6886	< 0.001
Ner_count	0.402323	0.862872	0.847246	0.681109	0.4734	< 0.001	
ObjectCQ	Word_count	7.896515	2.769706	7.855133	3.344069	0.0882	< 0.001
	Verb_count	1.359029	0.666083	1.225976	0.634546	0.1073	< 0.001
	Noun_count	2.219113	1.327125	2.754042	1.537968	0.2102	< 0.001
	Adj_count	0.477825	0.653557	0.340607	0.581339	0.1080	< 0.001
	Adv_count	0.015839	0.124887	0.016958	0.135094	-	-
	Pron_count	0.003696	0.060697	0.008282	0.092072	-	-
	Conj_count	0.030623	0.17234	0.012883	0.113936	-	-
	Prep_count	0.684266	0.703621	0.712633	0.701583	0.0240	< 0.001
	Modal_verb_count	0.004752	0.068788	0.001709	0.041307	-	-
	Unique_word_count	7.68849	2.609079	7.641777	3.090298	0.0882	< 0.001
	Stop_word_count	2.892819	1.345149	2.413698	1.623725	0.2009	< 0.001
Ner_count	0.247624	0.568993	0.855922	0.635948	0.5386	< 0.001	

Table 5: Overview of aggregated *statistics-based* features extracted from human-annotated (WDV-CQ-HA subset) and RevOnt-generated (WDV-CQ-RO subset) verbalisations and competency questions. Notation is consistent with Table 4.

Type	Feature	WDV-CQ-HA		WDV-CQ-RO		Statistical test	
		μ	σ	μ	σ	KS Statistic	p-value
Verbalisation	Flesch_kincaid_grade	5.1645	4.3038	6.8234	5.4145	0.1696	< 0.001
	Coleman_liau	6.7585	6.9995	11.2218	10.4399	0.3544	< 0.001
	Automated_readability	4.9664	5.3694	9.3776	14.7070	0.3638	< 0.001
	Gunning_fog	6.6066	4.3905	8.9610	5.4593	0.2105	< 0.001
	Dale_chall_readability	9.0684	4.3007	13.3295	6.5789	0.4760	< 0.001
	Linsear_write	3.6367	1.8109	5.1159	2.9878	0.2371	< 0.001
SubjectCQ	Flesch_kincaid_grade	2.2204	4.2172	3.9923	3.4255	0.2393	< 0.001
	Coleman_liau	1.5207	6.0379	5.6575	4.6460	0.3771	< 0.001
	Automated_readability	1.1825	4.4910	4.2432	4.0083	0.3626	< 0.001
	Gunning_fog	4.9301	4.3180	6.8362	4.3812	0.3436	< 0.001
	Dale_chall_readability	6.7107	4.5744	9.1959	3.1029	0.2597	< 0.001
	Linsear_write	2.4029	1.4958	3.9192	1.9726	0.3359	< 0.001
PropertyCQ	Flesch_kincaid_grade	6.0499	4.1777	1.1599	7.4969	0.5381	< 0.001
	Coleman_liau	8.4990	5.6713	3.9016	9.1768	0.3069	< 0.001
	Automated_readability	6.6017	3.9172	4.8573	4.5096	0.2536	< 0.001
	Gunning_fog	8.6725	3.4422	5.6077	5.0341	0.4506	< 0.001
	Dale_chall_readability	8.2708	2.5979	8.8422	4.3962	0.2439	< 0.001
	Linsear_write	5.2887	2.0900	2.5093	2.1629	0.6004	< 0.001
ObjectCQ	Flesch_kincaid_grade	3.5927	3.1698	2.6648	6.6696	0.1449	< 0.001
	Coleman_liau	5.5235	5.3804	5.4988	8.0585	0.1294	< 0.001
	Automated_readability	4.0484	4.1828	5.2317	4.2196	0.1492	< 0.001
	Gunning_fog	5.5520	4.1198	6.5423	5.0143	0.1262	< 0.001
	Dale_chall_readability	7.3251	3.8126	9.3388	3.9111	0.2759	< 0.001
	Linsear_write	2.7394	1.1107	3.1702	2.1217	0.1863	< 0.001